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Deliverable D2.1 - *Vulnerability pitfalls and gaps in adaptive capacity of citizens and stakeholders in key pilots*

WP2 – *Co-Design and Co-Creation of Innovative/Improved Tools/Actions for Local Communities*

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

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List of Acronyms

ACEA	Azienda Comunale Energia ed Ambiente
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
ATO2	Ambito Territoriale Ottimale 2
BoG	Breakout Group
CIMA	Centro Internazionale in Monitoraggio Ambientale
CMCC	Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici
EACC	Estrategia Aragonesa de Cambio Climático
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EU	European Union
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IW	Inception Workshop
NbS	nature-based solutions
SEI	Stockholm Environment Institute
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TG	Target Groups
UHI	Urban Heat Island
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

As the impacts of climate change intensify across Europe, the need to understand and strengthen local adaptive capacity has become increasingly urgent. Climate-related risks are affecting communities across environmental, social, and economic dimensions, often in complex and region-specific ways. To address these challenges, the Adaptation AGORA project aims to develop participatory tools and approaches that support local authorities, stakeholders, and citizens in co-designing equitable, effective, and context-sensitive adaptation strategies.

This deliverable reports on the work undertaken as part of Task 2.1 within Work Package 2 (WP2), which focuses on updating climate vulnerability assessments in four pilot locations: Malmö (Sweden), the Aragón Region (Spain), the City of Rome (Italy), and the City of Dresden (Germany). The task builds on existing climate risk data and combines it with local knowledge and stakeholder perspectives, gathered through inception workshops, to enhance understanding of vulnerabilities and inform future adaptation measures.

The workshops served as critical entry points for engaging with local actors, diagnosing context-specific climate impacts, and identifying key adaptive challenges and opportunities. The participatory approach employed in each pilot allowed for the co-production of knowledge and highlighted both systemic gaps and existing community strengths that can be leveraged in adaptation planning. The workshops tried to provide tailored solutions to local communities, through a bottom-up approach, in contrast to previous literature approaches, where a top-down approach is considered generally.

The structure of this report is as follows: Section 2 outlines the overall objectives of the Adaptation AGORA project, WP2, and Task 2.1, and describes its links to other tasks. It also provides a literature review on relevant themes including governance, planning, public engagement, equality, and eco-anxiety, as well as an overview of prior vulnerability assessments conducted in each pilot area. Section 3 details the overarching methodological approach and specific participatory tools used during the inception workshops. Section 4 presents the findings from each workshop, focusing on how they contributed to updating local vulnerability assessments. Section 5 discusses the implications of the findings and proposes the next steps for the continuation of Adaptation AGORA activities. The annexes contain the full reports from each pilot workshop.

2. Background

2.1 Objectives

2.1.1 Of Adaptation AGORA

Adaptation AGORA's ambition is to contribute to building climate change adaptation roadmaps in a transdisciplinary approach by fostering the participation and engagement of citizens and stakeholders in the co-design and co-creation of innovative problem-oriented climate adaptation solutions, promoting at the same time climate justice, gender equality, equity, and increasing adaptive capacity and citizens' empowerment to proactively support decision-making processes. Different communities and regions are involved in the project as pilots to foster climate change adaptation by co-evaluating existing best practices and promoting actions of co-design, co-development, and co-implementation in synergy with experts in different sectors engaging with communities and regions joining the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. Adaptation AGORA performs specific-context in-person activities in four key pilot regions in ensuring a broader involvement of communities and regions in the Mission's framework, and turning the project into a vehicle to serve the Mission itself.

2.1.2 Of Adaptation AGORA WP2

The Adaptation AGORA WP2 aims to co-create innovative mechanisms and approaches to engage citizens and stakeholders in transformative processes. It carries out activities in four pilot regions to assess local climate vulnerability, involve citizens in tackling disinformation, co-evaluate innovative mechanisms and approaches for citizen engagement in climate change adaptation, and co-design and co-create innovative climate adaptation solutions.

2.1.3 Of Adaptation AGORA Task 2.1

Task 2.1 contributes to identifying, building and establishing connections and alliances with communities and regions. To enlarge this network, it also capitalises on key pilots from projects and initiatives identified within Task 1.1 and clustered within Task 6.3. Four local inception face-to-face workshops were organised with pilot regions located within the action areas of the Adaptation AGORA project partners to identify vulnerability pitfalls and gaps in their adaptive capacity through climate vulnerability assessments, bringing adaptation needs and priorities in line with the needs of local communities (soft adaptation measure). Deliverable D2.1 aims to collect the outcomes of the four inception workshops (IWs), making a basis for a critical comparison between different regions and with cutting-edge literature.

2.1.4 Links to other tasks

Local communities reached and established during the activities of T2.1 were the starting point of co-creation workshops organised within T2.3 including citizens, civil society, academics, experts, and policy-makers in each of the four pilot regions to jointly evaluate innovative mechanisms and

approaches for involving citizens in climate change adaptation identified in WP1. The T2.1 activities helped to initiate a discussion with relevant stakeholders, to better understand how the cities can adapt to climate change, to better identify the target groups and to understand at the local level the priorities and the topics to be discussed in T2.3 and T2.4. Stakeholders further assisted the pilots in mapping citizen target groups and identifying relevant institutions and contacts. Their involvement aimed to incorporate their interests and priorities into defining the key issues for adaptation solutions, ensuring these solutions were locally relevant and promoting their potential future implementation.

2.2 Key topics

Since these topics will be often recalled during the deliverable, it is better to recall their definition as it has been discussed in several Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reports, particularly in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6):

ADAPTATION: Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities. Various types of adaptation can be distinguished, including anticipatory and reactive adaptation, private and public adaptation, and autonomous and planned adaptation (IPCC, 2022).

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY: it is the capability of a system (whether an ecosystem, community, or economy) to cope with and adapt to climate impacts through changes in practices, infrastructure, governance, and behaviour (IPCC, 2022).

CO-CREATION: Collaboratively creating outputs like tools or policy recommendations. A process that can add value and increase innovative potential through intentional experience design (Rill et Hämäläinen, 2018, Adaptation AGORA Deliverable D3.2 - Refined and updated framework to co-evaluate citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies).

CO-EVALUATION: To validate potential solutions or partial solutions to a particular challenge or issue jointly with one or more people. This implies considering available information, processes and how adequate the solution is in meeting the needs and expectations of stakeholders (Adaptation AGORA Deliverable D3.2 - Refined and updated framework to co-evaluate citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies).

CO-DESIGN: To create ways in which challenges can be addressed together with one or more people, implementing different methodologies and/or approaches such as lateral thinking to propose innovative solutions to current pressing climate change-related issues. It may also include devising effective and sustainable problem-solving techniques and strategies directly applicable to the challenges that need to be addressed (Cambridge Dictionary, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/co-design>, Adaptation AGORA Deliverable

D3.2 - Refined and updated framework to co-evaluate citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies).

SOFT ADAPTATION MEASURES: they refer to non-structural approaches to climate adaptation that focus on changes in behaviour, policies, governance, and capacity-building rather than physical infrastructure or technological interventions. These measures aim to enhance resilience through education, social systems, and institutional adjustments. For instance, informing communities about climate risks and adaptive behaviours (e.g., heatwave preparedness, water conservation) (IPCC, 2022).

VULNERABILITY in CC adaptation: is the propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected. Vulnerability encompasses a variety of concepts and elements, including sensitivity or susceptibility to harm and lack of capacity to cope and adapt (IPCC, 2022).

VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT: it is a systematic process used to evaluate the degree to which a system (e.g., community, sector, ecosystem) is susceptible to, or unable to cope with, the adverse effects of climate change. It helps identify risks, prioritise adaptation measures, and inform decision-making (IPCC, 2022).

2.3 Literature review

Early Developments

The academic discourse on climate adaptation began modestly, with early studies primarily exploring the implications of climatic variability on agriculture, meteorology, and economic systems. One of the earliest recorded contributions was by Folley (1978), who investigated the relationship between climatic variations and horticultural trade flows in Europe—demonstrating the economic sensitivity to weather patterns. During this initial period, research tended to be sector-specific and largely empirical, with limited integration of broader socio-political or environmental dimensions. Adaptation was often viewed as a residual outcome of mitigation failure (Burton et al., 1993), and the dominant focus remained on physical impacts rather than systemic resilience or institutional responses. Overall, publications during this era were sparse, representing only about 10% of the total climate adaptation literature (Nalau & Verrall, 2021).

Thematic Expansion and Institutional Focus

From 2000 onwards, climate adaptation emerged as a more structured and interdisciplinary field. The early 2000s witnessed a surge in interest in the natural sciences and environmental studies, with research expanding to include themes such as vulnerability, resilience, and adaptive capacity (Adger, 2006). Influential work during this decade introduced frameworks for assessing social vulnerability and the determinants of adaptive responses across scales (Smit & Wandel, 2006; Turner et al., 2003). The concept of resilience—especially in relation to disaster risk reduction—also gained prominence (Folke, 2006). Institutions became central to adaptation discourse, as scholars investigated the role of governance structures, planning systems, and decentralisation in shaping

local and national adaptive capacities (Betsill & Bulkeley, 2006). This period laid the groundwork for integrating adaptation into policy and development planning, though attention remained concentrated in the Global North, particularly in urban and agricultural contexts.

Acceleration and Diversification

The last decade has seen a marked acceleration and diversification of climate adaptation research. More than half of the existing literature has been published since 2010 (Nalau & Verrall, 2021), reflecting growing international urgency, increased funding, and enhanced global policy attention through mechanisms like the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2015). There has been a substantial broadening of thematic focus, including critical areas such as food security, health impacts, social capital, and the limits to adaptation (Adger et al., 2009; Ford et al., 2015). Meanwhile, urban contexts have become increasingly central, with concepts such as urban resilience, urban planning, and the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect gaining scholarly traction from 2011 onward (Anguelovski et al., 2016; Ziervogel et al., 2017).

Simultaneously, novel and cross-cutting topics have emerged, including green infrastructure, gender-sensitive adaptation, climate-smart agriculture, participatory governance, and climate finance (Taylor, 2018; Nightingale et al., 2020). The adoption of ecosystem-based adaptation and nature-based solutions (NbS) reflects a paradigm shift toward integrating biodiversity and ecological sustainability into adaptive planning (Chausson et al., 2020; Seddon et al., 2021). However, despite the thematic diversification, there remain significant geographical imbalances, with adaptation research continuing to be dominated by developed countries. As a result, insights from developing regions—particularly those most vulnerable to climate impacts—remain underrepresented (Ford et al., 2016).

Although long-standing topics such as vulnerability, mitigation, resilience, and water resources have retained consistent prominence, other themes have experienced dynamic shifts. Disaster risk reduction and sustainability have risen sharply in priority, while focus on policy, risk communication, and natural hazard modelling has shown signs of decline. Notably, the most recent years have prioritised more localised and inclusive adaptation strategies—reflecting a turn towards community participation, social justice, and climate equity in both research and practice. Overall, three predominant themes can be highlighted and better described in the following paragraphs:

- *policy, governance and aspects of planning*: the role of governance in climate change adaptation has focused mostly on institutions assessing the adaptive capacity of society particularly in urban areas.
- *vulnerability to climate change* (mostly focused on small islands and developing countries): including resilience (mostly disaster risk reduction) to climate change and its relation to natural hazards. Furthermore, a considerable amount of resilience research focuses on disaster risk reduction.

- *climate change risks*: including risk assessment, risk management and decision making, risk perceptions and the communication of risks, adaptive management and extreme weather.

2.3.1 Policy, governance and aspects of planning

Biesbroek et al. (2022) highlight that national legislation on climate adaptation saw significant growth around 2008 but stabilised around 2015. As a result, adaptation policies that were expected to emerge following the Paris Agreement remain relatively limited. Some critical policy issues struggle to gain the attention of national governments. However, compared to the past—when only a few topics dominated—recent National Communications show a more balanced distribution of attention across a wider range of issues. This shift may indicate a growing recognition of climate change impacts, increased research and reporting by governments, and a rise in awareness, ambition, and preparedness.

At the global level, political attention to climate adaptation has been shaped by key factors such as increasing confidence in scientific evidence from international organisations and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), political turmoil surrounding the Copenhagen Accord, and growing public pressure for policy action in response to rising awareness of climate change. On a regional scale, policy dynamics have been influenced by more localised factors, including direct experiences with climate impacts and extreme events, historical policy trajectories, variations in political cultures regarding climate policymaking, and patterns of policy convergence and imitation among countries within the same region. Regionally, adaptation topics are more prominent in Asia and, to a lesser extent, in Africa compared to Europe and North America. This likely reflects the urgent need for the most vulnerable countries to invest in adaptation, the early experiences with adaptation in these regions, or even signs of a transition toward transformative adaptation and long-term resilience.

In low- and middle-income countries in the Global South, adaptation priorities focus on disaster risk management and water-related challenges, including precipitation, drought, flooding, and the vulnerability of low-lying coastal areas. In North America, the strong emphasis on vulnerability and governance is striking and may stem from a growing focus on extreme weather events and disaster risk management. In Europe, adaptation remains a relatively minor policy concern, despite EU incentives to integrate adaptation measures into national climate frameworks. However, European countries still tend to prioritise studying climate impacts over implementing adaptation strategies. These regional differences raise important questions about the "optimal" balance between impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability in policy attention, the implications for policy design, and how these considerations translate into action on the ground.

2.3.2 Vulnerability to climate change

Vulnerability is a central concept in climate change adaptation research and policy, yet it remains multifaceted and context-dependent. It is commonly defined as the degree to which a system, community, or individual is susceptible to, or unable to cope with, the adverse effects of climate

change, including variability and extremes (IPCC, 2014). Earlier interpretations of vulnerability often emphasised biophysical exposure—particularly in hazard- and risk-oriented disciplines—focusing on the probability and magnitude of climate events and their impacts on human settlements or ecosystems. Over time, however, this understanding has expanded to incorporate social, economic, institutional, and political dimensions, reflecting a shift towards a more integrated and systemic conceptualisation.

A foundational contribution to this evolution is Adger's (2006) work, which highlighted that vulnerability is shaped not only by physical exposure but also by the ability to access resources, participate in decision-making, and exert agency. This broader framing aligns with the view that vulnerability is socially constructed and unevenly distributed across populations, with marginalised groups often facing disproportionate risks. For instance, Smit and Wandel (2006) argue that vulnerability is dynamic, influenced by historical, economic, and institutional factors that interact across scales. Their work, along with others such as Turner et al. (2003), laid the groundwork for analysing vulnerability within coupled social-ecological systems, where feedback and thresholds are critical to resilience.

The literature has also differentiated between endogenous vulnerability—arising from internal characteristics of a system or community—and contextual vulnerability, which considers broader structural factors, including governance, inequality, and socio-political exclusion (Eriksen & O'Brien, 2007). This has prompted calls for more participatory and inclusive approaches to vulnerability assessment, especially in developing country contexts, where top-down risk models often fail to capture lived realities. Recent studies have paid closer attention to intersectional factors such as gender, age, ethnicity, and livelihood, highlighting the need to move beyond generic vulnerability metrics and embrace more nuanced, context-specific methodologies (Nightingale et al., 2020; Ford et al., 2016).

Recent literature has further underscored the deepening intersection between climate change, economic inequality, and vulnerability. Mejean et al. (2024) emphasise that the overwhelming majority of studies find climate change to be a powerful amplifier of economic disparities, disproportionately affecting lower-income populations across all regions, sectors, and types of inequality. This pattern is especially pronounced in cross-country analyses, revealing that poorer nations and households are systematically more exposed and less equipped to respond to climate-induced stressors. In light of this, national governments must urgently prioritise the equitable allocation of adaptation and loss-and-damage finance, ensuring that vulnerable households receive targeted support to reduce exposure and build resilience. However, Mejean et al. also highlight a major research gap: there remains no comprehensive global quantification of climate change's impacts on economic inequality across sectors—limiting the design of evidence-based policy interventions.

Climate change-related disasters further complicate this picture, as illustrated by Cappelli et al. (2021), who argue that such events are not merely physical phenomena but outcomes of a complex interplay between climatological, environmental, and socio-economic vulnerabilities. The impacts of disasters are highly differentiated both between and within countries, with marginalised and low-income groups facing disproportionately high losses and slower recovery times. As climate extremes become more frequent and intense, there is a growing risk that countries with high inequality may become locked into a feedback loop—where limited adaptive capacity leads to recurrent losses, further weakening resilience. Without structural reforms that address inequitable access to precautionary tools, early warning systems, healthcare, and insurance, such nations may find themselves unable to implement or sustain effective adaptation strategies. In this context, the framing of floods, droughts, and storms not as unexpected disasters but as predictable natural events becomes crucial. Equitable, inclusive adaptation requires pre-emptive policy design and investment, ensuring that those most at risk have the resources and capacities to withstand, recover from, and adapt to a rapidly changing climate.

In terms of empirical application, vulnerability assessments have become key tools in informing climate adaptation strategies, particularly in urban and agricultural settings. These assessments aim to identify populations, assets, or systems at risk and to prioritise actions that reduce exposure and build adaptive capacity. While early assessments relied heavily on quantitative indicators and spatial modelling, recent approaches increasingly emphasise the co-production of knowledge between scientists, policymakers, and communities (Tschakert et al., 2013). Public engagement—while not yet universally applied—is gaining recognition as a vital component in ensuring that vulnerability assessments are both locally relevant and socially just. Participatory mapping, citizen science, and deliberative workshops are among the methods used to incorporate diverse knowledge systems, enhance transparency, and foster ownership of adaptation outcomes. Nevertheless, challenges remain in institutionalising these practices and reconciling scientific rigour with participatory inclusivity.

2.3.3 Climate change risks

Climate change is reshaping the landscape of global risk, with increasingly frequent and severe impacts threatening ecosystems, infrastructure, economies, and communities. The risks associated with climate change are not limited to the physical environment but span a complex web of socio-economic and political vulnerabilities. The literature has thus evolved to approach climate change risks in an integrated, systemic manner—combining assessments of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability with adaptive responses and risk governance mechanisms.

A major shift in climate adaptation research occurred with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Fifth Assessment Report, which reframed climate impacts in terms of risk, emphasising that it results from the interaction of climate-related hazards with the exposure and vulnerability of human and natural systems (IPCC, 2014). This conceptual framing has enabled a

more nuanced understanding of how risks manifest and escalate, especially in complex socio-ecological systems. Tools and frameworks for risk assessment have increasingly integrated scenario-based and probabilistic approaches to capture uncertainty and support evidence-based policy planning (Field et al., 2012; Cardona et al., 2012).

Managing climate risks involves decision-making under uncertainty, where long-term planning is complicated by the unpredictability of climate outcomes and socio-political dynamics. As a result, adaptive and flexible decision-support methods have gained prominence. These include Robust Decision Making (Lempert et al., 2003), Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways (Haasnoot et al., 2013), and Real Options Analysis (Dobes, 2008). These frameworks support decisions that remain effective across a range of plausible futures and are particularly relevant in urban planning, coastal adaptation, and water resource management (Wise et al., 2014; Walker et al., 2013).

Another key aspect of managing climate risks is understanding risk perception and communication, which heavily influences public engagement, policy acceptance, and individual behavioural change. Research shows that risk perception is not purely rational but is shaped by cultural values, emotions, trust in institutions, and prior experiences (Weber, 2010; Leiserowitz et al., 2006). The Social Amplification of Risk Framework (Kasperson et al., 1988) explains how media, social networks, and cultural contexts amplify or downplay risks. Moser (2010) emphasises the need for tailored, empathetic communication that resonates with lived experiences rather than simply transmitting scientific data.

Climate risks are further magnified by the growing intensity and frequency of extreme weather events, including droughts, floods, heatwaves, and storms. These events test the resilience of both physical infrastructure and governance systems (Bouwer, 2011; Cutter et al., 2008). The concept of compound and cascading risks has gained attention, highlighting how multiple, interacting hazards can produce disproportionate and unpredictable impacts (Zscheischler et al., 2018; Raymond et al., 2020).

To effectively manage these escalating risks, adaptive management has emerged as a preferred approach. Originally rooted in ecological resilience theory (Holling, 1978), adaptive management promotes iterative decision-making, learning-by-doing, and stakeholder co-production of knowledge. It supports responses that evolve as new information emerges or as conditions change (Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Armitage et al., 2008).

Finally, the literature increasingly emphasises transformational adaptation—a departure from incremental adjustments toward more profound shifts in social, institutional, and infrastructural systems, particularly where current approaches are insufficient to address high-impact, low-probability risks (Kates et al., 2012; Tschakert et al., 2013). Nature-based solutions, ecosystem-based adaptation, and green infrastructure are part of this shift, offering sustainable pathways to reduce climate risks while enhancing co-benefits for biodiversity and human well-being (Kabisch et al., 2017; Chausson et al., 2020).

In conclusion, climate change risks demand adaptive, multi-dimensional, and inclusive strategies that bridge scientific rigour with local relevance. The integration of physical and social science, participatory governance, and flexible decision-making approaches is vital for understanding and responding to the evolving climate risk landscape.

2.3.4 Other relevant topics

Owen (2020) underscores the importance of ensuring diverse representation in the knowledge and expertise that inform adaptation initiatives. Similarly, Huegel and Davies (2019) identify a persistent lack of shared understanding concerning public participation in climate adaptation across different disciplines. Many participatory processes remain incomplete or fragmented, with inconsistent engagement of the public and local communities. Furthermore, key concepts—such as risk, vulnerability, and adaptive capacity—are interpreted and applied differently across academic fields and among various stakeholder groups.

A critical examination of risk-related themes, particularly concerning flooding, reveals significant gaps in perception, communication, and awareness. Effective interdisciplinary collaboration requires a shared conceptual framework for understanding public participation, citizen engagement, and the use of influential risk-related concepts across diverse contexts.

Research on public engagement in climate adaptation has predominantly been shaped by scholars from high-income countries. Nevertheless, emerging economies are increasingly contributing to cross-national and interdisciplinary studies. These efforts span geographical and disciplinary boundaries, enriching the global discourse on adaptation and justice.

Coffey et al. (2021) report that certain vulnerable populations—including young people, Indigenous communities, and those with strong cultural or spiritual ties to nature—are disproportionately affected by eco-anxiety. In particular, children and adolescents may experience emotional, psychological, and even spiritual distress related to the climate crisis. Despite being among the most impacted, Indigenous peoples remain underrepresented in both research and policymaking.

Leger-Goodes et al. (2022) argue that, in adults, the potentially pathological dimensions of eco-anxiety are highly context-specific. As such, eco-anxiety should not be prematurely classified as a psychological disorder. In some cases, it may have empowering effects, motivating individuals to engage in climate action. Children who develop strong emotional responses along with positive coping mechanisms may experience increased hope and engagement. Conversely, others may feel overwhelmed and powerless, resulting in emotional paralysis, learned hopelessness, or denial.

Effective climate adaptation activities typically share common characteristics: collaborative decision-making, equitable distribution of physical, financial, and informational resources, and integrative strategies that enhance human well-being, institutional relationships, and environmental security. These strategies are often synergistic, becoming more effective when implemented collectively rather than in isolation. Evaluation indicators are essential to track

adaptation justice and equity, including aspects such as leadership structures, decision-making processes, exclusion from authority, communication and accessibility, recognition of different forms of knowledge, and the fair distribution of adaptation benefits.

2.4 Climate risks and vulnerability analyses for the pilot regions

In this section, we report a detailed analysis of the local impact and vulnerabilities of the four key pilot regions highlighting the local climate change impacts, the key vulnerabilities and the adaptation gaps and challenges.

2.4.1 Malmö, Sweden

In Malmö, Adaptation AGORA has focused on urban heat vulnerability while also identifying other local climate change impacts, vulnerabilities, and adaptation gaps. While not exhaustive, these findings underscore the most pressing concerns raised by local stakeholders. For a detailed examination of urban heat vulnerability, please refer to the co-authored Adaptation AGORA report published by the City of Malmö: *Extremvärme i Malmö: Vem drabbas och hur kan vi lindra effekterna?* (Extreme Heat in Malmö: Who is Affected and How Can We Mitigate the Effects?) (2024).

Local climate change impacts in Malmö

Malmö is situated in Scania in the southernmost region of Sweden. Scania is predicted as one of the regions at the most risk of the impacts of climate change in the country. The whole region is expected to experience an increase in flooding, erosion, and sea level rise (Brink & Wamsler, 2018). Specifically, the city of Malmö faces significant exposure to coastal flooding, extreme precipitation, and heatwaves and droughts, all of which are intensified by climate change.

Extreme precipitation: It is anticipated that extreme precipitation events will become more frequent and intense due to climate change, resulting in increased flooding and disruptions to critical infrastructure. A notable example of this phenomenon occurred during the 2014 cloudburst when Malmö experienced a record-breaking rainfall of about 100 mm within a 6-hour period. Extreme rainfall overwhelms the stormwater system, leading to street flooding, traffic disruption, damaged buildings, and considerable inconvenience for both residents and visitors of Malmö (City of Malmö, 2023).

Sea-level rise and storm surges: Sea-level rise and storm surges pose significant risks to Malmö, which has a coastline of 43 km. The city is particularly vulnerable to coastal flooding resulting from storm surges. In the context of a changing climate, rising sea levels are projected to impact the coastline negatively, with the greatest impact in southern Sweden due to its limited land rise (City of Malmö, 2023).

Heatwaves and droughts: Malmö is expected to face an increase in the frequency and intensity of heatwaves as climate change progresses, a situation exacerbated by UHI effects in densely populated areas (City of Malmö, 2024a). During the 2018 heatwave, Sweden recorded an excess mortality rate of 700 individuals significantly affecting vulnerable groups including those in eldercare, homecare services, and preschools (The Public Health Agency of Sweden, 2019).

Key vulnerabilities

Ageing and growing population: The demographic trends in Malmö indicate a significant increase in both the overall population as well as the elderly residents. With around 362,000 inhabitants Malmö is the third largest and the fastest growing city in Sweden. The population is projected to increase by 40,000 by the year 2034. However, the current housing supply is insufficient to meet the growing demand, despite new construction initiatives. Moreover, the increasing urban density is intensifying the UHI effect. Notably, during this same period, residents aged 80 years and older represent the fastest growing age group within the population (City of Malmö, 2024b).

Inequalities: Around 22% of residents experience a low economic standard. However, income segregation is pronounced across neighbourhoods and demographics. Poverty is twice as common among foreign-born residents. Furthermore, inequalities are growing, so residents face unequal access to housing, resources and opportunities (City of Malmö, 2019).

Workforce: As temperatures continue to rise, the workforce, particularly outdoor workers engaged in physically demanding occupations, faces increased risks related to heat-related issues. This situation not only leads to reduced productivity but also increased health concerns (City of Malmö, 2024b).

Built environment: The built environment in Malmö has traditionally been constructed to retain heat during the cold winter months. The landscape is largely characterized by extensive hard surfaces, and the existing stormwater management systems lack the capacity to effectively manage and divert heavy rainfall (City of Malmö, 2023).

Adaptation gaps and challenges

From the experience in Malmö, two major challenges stand out for effective and equitable adaptation. Notably, both citizens and the city administration hold significant knowledge relevant to adaptation.

Inadequate financial and legal instruments: The existing national adaptation policies demonstrate shortcomings in terms of defining clear roles and responsibilities, providing incentives, and allocating financial resources for municipalities to effectively tackle climate change. Additionally, heatwaves are not covered within the framework of binding legislation (Swedish Expert Council for Climate Change Adaptation, 2022). These challenges mirror the city administration's experience in Malmö.

Insufficient attention to social vulnerability and justice: There is a notable lack of attention to social vulnerability and justice in the context of climate adaptation in Swedish municipalities. These municipalities are responsible for translating national adaptation objectives into actionable measures. Although they are mandated to conduct risk and vulnerability assessments, these frequently overlook social vulnerabilities (Barquet et al. 2023). The integration of socially informed approaches into adaptation remains in the early stages in municipalities, including Malmö, apart from pilot initiatives focused on interactive vulnerability visualisation tools (Opach et al. 2020) and methods for analysing climate risk in property portfolios (Hjerpe et al. 2020). Additionally, issues related to power dynamics, inequality and injustice are largely absent from Swedish adaptation strategies (Barquet et al. 2023), including those implemented in Malmö.

2.4.2 Aragón Region, Spain

Aragón Region, located in northeastern Spain, is experiencing increasing climate-related challenges that threaten its environment, economy, and communities. The Estrategia Aragonesa de Cambio Climático (EACC 2030) outlines the region's response, focusing on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting renewable energy, and integrating climate policies into all levels of governance.

As climate change intensifies, Aragón is already experiencing tangible environmental shifts, from rising temperatures and prolonged droughts to increasing risks of wildfires and biodiversity loss, all of which threaten the region's natural and economic stability.

Local climate change impacts in Aragón Region

Rising Temperatures and Extreme Weather: Climate projections indicate a significant increase in average temperatures across Aragón, particularly affecting summer months. This rise in temperatures contributes to more frequent and intense heatwaves, droughts, and wildfires, especially in the Ebro Valley and forested areas.

Water Scarcity and Desertification: Aragón's semi-arid climate makes it particularly vulnerable to declining water resources. Reduced rainfall and increased evaporation due to higher temperatures are expected to lower river flow levels, particularly in the Ebro River basin, which supplies water for agriculture, industry, and urban areas. Desertification risks are also growing, particularly in rural and agricultural lands.

Threats to Agriculture and Food Security: The region's agricultural sector, a key component of its economy, faces severe risks from climate change. Rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall, and increased irrigation demands threaten crop yields and soil health. The livestock sector, particularly pig farming, is also at risk due to heat stress and higher methane emissions, necessitating urgent adaptation strategies.

Impact on Biodiversity and Natural Ecosystems: Aragón's diverse ecosystems, from the Pyrenees to the Ebro Valley, are at risk due to shifting climate conditions. Rising temperatures force species to

migrate to higher altitudes, reducing viable habitats. Additionally, wetlands and forests face increased threats from wildfires, droughts, and invasive species, further endangering local biodiversity.

UHI Effect and Infrastructure Vulnerability: Cities in Aragón, particularly Zaragoza, are increasingly affected by the UHI effect, amplifying the impact of heatwaves. Extreme precipitation events also pose a growing risk, overwhelming stormwater systems and increasing flood hazards. Sustainable urban planning, including green infrastructure and energy-efficient buildings, is essential to enhance climate resilience.

Key vulnerabilities

Water Dependency and Rural Challenges: Aragón's reliance on water-intensive agriculture makes it particularly vulnerable to droughts and changing precipitation patterns. Rural areas, many of which are already struggling with depopulation, have limited capacity to adapt to these challenges. The decline in water availability could further drive economic instability and land degradation.

Social and Economic Inequalities: The effects of climate change disproportionately impact Aragón's most vulnerable populations, including elderly residents, low-income communities, and those living in rural areas. Many of these groups have limited access to cooling systems, adaptive infrastructure, and financial resources to mitigate climate risks. Addressing these inequalities is a priority within the EACC 2030.

Governance and Policy Gaps: While Aragón has a strong climate strategy aligned with national and EU policies, local implementation remains a challenge. The region needs improved coordination, increased financial investment, and stronger regulatory frameworks to ensure effective adaptation measures.

Transition to a Low-Carbon Economy: The closure of Aragón's coal-fired power plants presents both economic challenges and opportunities. While the region is investing in renewable energy, the transition to a low-carbon economy requires further development in green jobs, circular economy models, and sustainable industries.

2.4.3 City of Rome, Italy

The Italian pilot case focused on the city of Rome. In this context, Adaptation AGORA provided support for the development of the Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, which was approved during the course of the project. Therefore, among the various sectors actually impacted by climate change, all those sectors that were considered within the Strategy and are expected to be most exposed to climate change impacts in the short, medium, and long term for the City of Rome were analysed.

They are:

- water (understood both as resource management and as impacts related to rainfall);

- urban settlements;
- networks and infrastructures;
- cultural heritage;
- health;
- the socio-economic system;
- the marine and coastal system;
- the agricultural and livestock system;
- biodiversity and ecosystems.

With the aim of defining the main socio-economic vulnerabilities (e.g., inequalities), as well as structural and environmental vulnerabilities, and identifying key needs and criticalities related to the territory's adaptive capacity, a dedicated working space was carved out from the early stages of the activities in Rome. This was done to identify the challenges of vulnerability and gaps in adaptive capacity through climate vulnerability assessments, ensuring that adaptation needs and priorities are aligned with the needs of local communities.

For more information on the content presented in this chapter, please refer to the Climate Change Adaptation Strategy approved in early 2025 (Proposta di strategia di adattamento climatico, 2024).

Local climate change impacts in Rome

The IPCC has identified the Mediterranean as a global climate change hotspot, with significant temperature increases affecting both land and sea. Rome, as Italy's largest agricultural municipality and a key centre for tourism and economic activity, is particularly vulnerable.

Throughout its history, Rome has faced natural disasters, floods, and transformations that shaped its geography and society. Today, climate change poses new challenges but also offers opportunities for urban regeneration. The city is already experiencing the growing impacts of more frequent and intense floods and heavy rainfall, making the need for adaptation measures urgent and strategic for protecting its territory, economy, and communities.

Rapid Temperature Growth: The city of Rome is experiencing a steady and increasingly marked rise in average annual temperature. From 1971 to 2021, climate data show a clear upward trend, with a turning point in the early 1990s. Since 1991, annual temperature anomalies have almost consistently been positive, and the period from 2011 to 2021 recorded the highest temperatures ever observed. The decadal average temperature has risen from approximately 15.3°C (1971–1980) to 17.7°C (2011–2021), approaching an anomaly of +2°C compared to the 1971–2000 climatological reference. Notably, in 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018, the average annual temperature in Rome exceeded 18°C. This increase is due to rising minimum and maximum temperatures, with Rome showing the highest anomaly among Italian regional capitals (+1.6°C compared to the 1981–2010 baseline). This confirms Rome as one of the most affected cities by ongoing climate change in Italy.

Precipitation Variability and Increasing Extremes: From 1971 to 2021, the city has alternated between wet and dry years, with more frequent negative anomalies since the mid-1990s. The average annual precipitation, which was about 807 mm during the 1971-2000 period, decreased to 761 mm in the 1981-2010 period, then slightly increased to 783 mm in the most recent period (2011-2021). The driest years include 2017, with only 527 mm of rainfall, while 2014 was the wettest, with over 1,100 mm. This trend reflects strong fluctuations and extreme events, with periods of intense dryness followed by heavy rainfall concentrated in short intervals.

Drought Risk and Water Supply: Rome's water supply is managed by the Azienda Comunale Energia ed Ambiente (ACEA) Ambito Territoriale Ottimale 2 (ATO2), with the main sources being springs (84.6%) and wells (14.5%). The city's distribution network faces challenges due to ageing infrastructure, seismic risks, and lack of redundancy. In 2022, daily water distribution reached 1.1 million cubic meters, with 60% from the Peschiera-Capore aqueduct. With climate change intensifying droughts and rainfall extremes, the city's water resilience is under pressure. Efforts to reduce water losses have been effective, bringing the current loss rate to 27.8%, lower than the national average. Investments, including the "districting" of the network, have improved efficiency, saving 70 million cubic meters of water by 2021. Future goals include reducing losses to 25% by 2027, supported by "Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza" funding. These measures are crucial for ensuring water security in the face of ongoing drought risks.

Key vulnerabilities

The vulnerabilities listed below served as the starting point for structuring the collection of information on sector-specific vulnerabilities (i.e., water; urban settlements; networks and infrastructures; cultural heritage; health; the socio-economic system; the marine and coastal system; the agricultural and livestock system; biodiversity and ecosystems) and the lack of adaptive capacity associated with them.

Impact of Sewerage and Wastewater Treatment Infrastructure: Rome's sewerage and wastewater treatment system includes approximately 4,000 km of sewer network, 224 pumping stations, and 33 treatment plants. Despite ongoing efforts to extend services, some peripheral neighbourhoods lack proper sewage connections. The Crescenza Collector project, completed in 2023, will connect 80,000 residents in northern Rome. The city's ageing sewage network, especially in historic areas, requires frequent repairs due to damage from wear and previous interventions. Inspections and better coordination among service managers are essential. Wastewater treatment plants process 85% of the total volume managed by ACEA ATO 2 Spa, with real-time monitoring of treated water launched in 2021.

Hydrogeological Risk: Rome faces significant hydrogeological risk, primarily due to its watercourses like the Tiber, which is prone to flooding. Despite past mitigation efforts, including embankments and the Corbara Dam, these measures are insufficient against increasingly frequent and intense flash floods. Studies have identified high-risk areas in the city, such as Acquatraversa, Malafede, and

Ostia, and proposed over 110 interventions to reduce flood risk. The fragmented management of the hydraulic network and lack of maintenance exacerbate these risks, highlighting the need for a coordinated approach. Additionally, landslides and debris flows are a growing issue due to the city's steep hills and inadequate vegetation management. The ancient network of underground cavities, coupled with modern urbanization, also increases the likelihood of sinkholes. Addressing these risks requires ongoing, coordinated efforts, substantial resources, and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Impact on the Hydrological System: Rome's hydro-geological system is shaped by the Tevere river and its tributaries, with urbanization and climate change increasing flood risks, especially from intense rainfall and flash floods. Over 400,000 people are vulnerable to these hazards. The city's flood management strategies need to account for changing climate conditions, such as rising temperatures and reduced rainfall, which may alter hydrological processes. Urbanization and small sub-basins amplify flood risks, requiring targeted adaptation measures for future resilience.

Groundwater Resources and Monitoring: Rome's water supply mainly comes from distant springs, but significant groundwater resources are stored underground in natural aquifers. These aquifers are primarily volcanic and alluvial, creating complex underground water circulation. Groundwater monitoring is essential due to the city's infrastructure and local use for industrial and irrigation purposes. Over 200 wells are measured biannually, with some stations using automatic sensors for continuous monitoring. A web-GIS system has been developed to record and visualize real-time data, including piezometric levels, conductivity, pH, and temperature, offering key insights into groundwater flow.

Impact of Climate Change on Biodiversity: Rome's biodiversity, shaped by its diverse environments, is increasingly threatened by climate change. Rising temperatures, reduced rainfall, and increased summer aridity, especially in coastal areas, are altering plant distributions and ecosystems. Protected natural areas, which cover 67% of the city, are facing growing impacts, including the UHI effect, water stress, and heightened wildfire risks. To safeguard biodiversity, climate adaptation policies must focus on preserving green spaces, improving ecosystem services, and addressing the interconnected challenges of climate change and biodiversity loss.

Ecosystem Services in Urban and Peri-Urban Areas: Rome's ecosystems are increasingly vulnerable to climate change, particularly due to the UHI effect and pollution. Areas with high vegetation, like Castelporziano, help mitigate these impacts, but urbanized zones with less greenery face heightened risks. Green spaces such as urban forests and street trees play a critical role in cooling and air quality, yet climate change threatens their sustainability. Strengthening Nature-Based Solutions and Rome's Ecological Network is essential to enhance resilience, protect biodiversity, and address climate-related challenges.

Coastal Erosion from Sea Level Rise: The Lazio Region's 360 km coastline, particularly around Rome, has been heavily impacted by erosion, especially since the 1960s due to reduced sediment transport from the Tiber River. Despite interventions like beach nourishment and protective structures, the

coastline continues to erode, with the area of natural beach surface decreasing significantly from 159 km² in 2000 to 95 km² in 2020. Coastal dynamics have shown an increase in erosion-affected areas, while the region's beach systems alternate between erosion and recovery. Future sea level rise projections highlight further risks to low-lying coastal zones, requiring continued adaptation efforts.

Urban Settlements and Infrastructure: A study by the University of Roma Tre and the “Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile” (2014) mapped climate vulnerability across Rome’s urban areas, identifying key risks like heatwaves and flooding. The analysis focused on 1900 neighbourhoods, revealing higher vulnerability in densely urbanized areas, especially in the southern-western parts of the city. These areas, once swamps, are prone to flooding due to inadequate infrastructure. The study underscores the need for improved urban planning, green spaces, and flood defences to address these vulnerabilities.

Cultural Heritage: The cultural heritage of the Metropolitan City of Rome is increasingly vulnerable to climate change and pollution, with key risks including erosion of marble and limestone monuments, thermal stress leading to damage in marble structures, and accelerated biological degradation due to rising temperatures. Additionally, increased humidity cycles are expected to cause salt crystallization in porous materials, damaging historical buildings and archaeological sites. These threats highlight the need for detailed studies to assess and mitigate the risks to cultural assets.

Agriculture and Livestock: Rome’s agricultural system, covering 45% of the municipal area, mainly relies on extensive farming and livestock production. Key sectors include cereal farming, livestock, and horticulture. Climate change poses several risks, such as higher summer temperatures, altered rainfall patterns, and increased extreme weather events. These could reduce crop yields, particularly for forage and grains, and lead to the shift to less water-intensive crops. Additionally, fruit crops may suffer from sunburn, and livestock production could face forage shortages. Flooding in areas with poor drainage is also a risk. Adaptation strategies are essential to protect these sectors from climate impacts.

Socio-Economic Impacts and Public Health: Climate change exacerbates socio-economic and health vulnerabilities, particularly for disadvantaged populations. Extreme weather events like heatwaves and floods disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, including the elderly, children, ethnic minorities, immigrants, and those with pre-existing health conditions. In urban areas, the UHI effect intensifies temperatures, while high pollution levels further compromise public health. Socio-economic factors, such as low income, low education levels, and poor living conditions, amplify the risks, with marginalized communities experiencing greater exposure and fewer resources to adapt. These vulnerabilities underscore the need for targeted interventions to address both environmental and social inequalities, focusing on the most at-risk populations.

Adaptation gaps and challenges

Mitigating Risks to Public Safety and Health: The increasing frequency of extreme rainfall, prolonged droughts, and heat waves heightens the vulnerability of natural, infrastructural, and residential systems. Certain neighbourhoods are at greater risk, particularly during river surges or coastal storms, as well as during heat waves. Addressing these risks requires a comprehensive understanding of local conditions to ensure effective early warning systems and emergency preparedness. Strengthening civil protection measures will help mitigate the most severe consequences.

Urban planning and infrastructure projects must incorporate climate adaptation strategies to minimize the impact of both intense rainfall—through measures such as underground cisterns—and extreme heat, ensuring safer and more liveable environments. Additionally, enhancing the soil's natural absorption capacity by increasing permeable spaces, reducing asphalt coverage, and planting more trees can help regulate temperatures and improve water management.

The Roman coastline, a fragile ecosystem, faces increasing erosion. Rising sea levels pose a significant threat to low-lying areas, and projections indicate a higher risk of saltwater intrusion. Coastal preservation efforts must be prioritized to protect both the environment and local communities.

Reducing Urban Heat and Improving Liveability: Heat waves in Rome have intensified, and in some districts, temperatures reach levels that endanger public health. The UHI effect—caused by impermeable surfaces, heat-absorbing materials like asphalt and concrete, and vehicle emissions—exacerbates this issue.

Adaptation efforts must focus on the most vulnerable neighbourhoods, particularly those with disadvantaged socioeconomic conditions and inadequate urban infrastructure for heat mitigation. Implementing NbS, such as increasing green spaces, incorporating reflective materials, and expanding water features for cooling, can significantly lower perceived temperatures while enhancing biodiversity and urban liveability.

Rethinking Rome's Relationship with Water and the Sea: Securing water access is a critical priority in the face of climate change. Rome currently has one of the lowest rates of water loss in Italy, and major investments are being made to improve water supply security and efficiency. However, the use of freshwater resources must be significantly reduced, as must groundwater extraction.

Innovative water conservation strategies should be adopted across domestic, agricultural, and industrial sectors, including increased reliance on rainwater harvesting and reclaimed water for non-potable uses, in line with European Directives.

Prioritizing the Most Vulnerable Neighbourhoods: Climate adaptation efforts should begin in the areas most at risk, where hydrogeological threats and heat-related health risks are highest. Preventative actions must be strengthened in these districts, alongside epidemiological monitoring to track health impacts in collaboration with the “Dipartimento di Epidemiologia del Servizio Sanitario Regionale del Lazio”. Community-based support networks should also be expanded to

increase public awareness and ensure access to services that can mitigate health risks, particularly among socially isolated individuals.

Building a Climate-Resilient Economy: Reports from the Bank of Italy and the National Climate Adaptation Plan highlight the economic risks associated with biodiversity loss, deteriorating social conditions, and workplace disruptions, all of which threaten economic growth.

In Rome, these risks affect industries, small businesses, and agriculture, which are increasingly impacted by extreme rainfall and water shortages. Sectors reliant on outdoor work must adapt to prolonged and intensified heat, requiring changes in work schedules, crop selection, and irrigation methods.

Tourism, a key economic driver for Rome, is also at risk. Satellite analyses show that the city centre consistently records the highest daytime temperatures, potentially deterring summer visitors. If adaptation strategies are not implemented, high temperatures could make the city less attractive to tourists, impacting the local economy.

2.4.4 City of Dresden, Germany

Local climate change impacts in Dresden

Dresden is facing rising temperatures with a steady increase in hot days (>30°C) and tropical nights (>20°C), exacerbated by UHI effects in densely built areas (LHD, 2025). Shifting precipitation patterns are causing drier summers and wetter winters, leading to higher drought risks, groundwater depletion, and increased flash flood events due to more frequent and intense heavy rainfall (Franke, 2015). These extreme weather events (i.e., longer heatwaves, stronger storms, and more intense rainfall) are also disrupting Dresden's infrastructure, e.g., through increasing flood damage to roads and bridges (Franke, 2015). The Elbe River and Dresden's urban drainage system are particularly vulnerable to flooding, as heavy rainfall and rising groundwater levels push drainage capacities to their limits, further intensified by urban expansion and continued soil sealing (LHD, 2025). These challenges demand urgent adaptation measures, such as expanding green infrastructure, improving flood resilience, and enhancing water management, as Dresden continues to address increasing climate vulnerabilities (City of Dresden, 2019).

Key vulnerabilities

Urban heat stress: Densely built districts such as Neustadt and Altstadt experience high overheating rates, with temperatures rising 3–5°C above surrounding open spaces (LHD, 2025). Beyond the challenges of climate change, Dresden's rapid urban growth—one of the highest in Germany—combined with an increasing proportion of vulnerable groups, such as the elderly and children, is exacerbating the issue. Increasing urban density, further intensified by poor air circulation and limited green spaces, is amplifying the UHI effect, posing risks to public health (City of Dresden, 2019).

Water management and flood risks: The combination of increased summer droughts and heavier winter precipitation stresses Dresden's water management system. Flooding risks are heightened along the Elbe River and in urban drainage systems that are ill-equipped for extreme rainfall. Therefore, the need for further action should be assessed on a regular basis (Franke, 2015).

Agriculture and forestry: Dresden's surrounding agricultural lands are increasingly exposed to summer droughts, reducing crop yields and increasing irrigation demands (a costly measure). Moreover, in Saxony (as in many parts of Central Europe) past forestry management practices negatively affected adaptive potential by promoting large-scale cultivation of a few tree species and origins that were often not adapted to the site. All of the above has resulted in local forests being threatened by more frequent droughts, wildfires, and pest infestations (Franke, 2015).

Adaptation Gaps and Challenges

Dresden faces significant adaptation gaps across multiple sectors, particularly in energy infrastructure, construction, urban planning, workforce conditions, economic resilience, and governance.

Underestimation of climate risks in business: The business sector underestimates climate risks, leading to insufficient preparation for extreme weather and disruptions in supply chains (TU Dresden, 2013a). In tourism, high temperatures and rising energy costs threaten urban tourism and the hospitality industry, while transport networks remain vulnerable to extreme weather events (TU Dresden, 2013b). The energy sector is increasingly vulnerable to extreme weather events, leading to power supply disruptions, rising cooling demands, and infrastructure damage from floods and storms (TU Dresden, 2013d). The high-tech industry, essential to Dresden's economy, faces supply chain disruptions and difficulty maintaining stable production conditions in temperature-sensitive environments like cleanrooms (TU Dresden, 2013e).

Infrastructures resilience: the construction sector struggles with rising costs of climate-resilient materials and the challenge of adjusting work schedules to mitigate heat stress while maintaining economic feasibility (TU Dresden, 2013c). Building infrastructure in Dresden remains insufficiently adapted, with outdated construction codes and rising cooling costs that exacerbate energy consumption (TU Dresden, 2013g). Flood protection remains another pressing issue, as the city's drainage systems struggle to cope with increasingly frequent heavy rainfall events. While Dresden has adopted a "sponge city" approach to improve water retention, further investment is needed to enhance decentralized rainwater management and reduce surface sealing (REGKLAM, 2013).

Health and climate change: the workforce is exposed to climate-related health risks, particularly outdoor workers and employees in poorly cooled buildings, leading to reduced productivity and increased health concerns (TU Dresden, 2013f).

Governance and funding: Gaps in governance and policy implementation hinder effective climate adaptation, with a need for better planning tools, policy coordination, and long-term risk

management strategies (REGKLAM, 2009). Funding constraints and administrative fragmentation continue to delay large-scale climate adaptation projects (LHD, 2025). Addressing these adaptation gaps require innovative financing models, regulatory updates, and sector-specific adaptation strategies, along with cross-sectoral collaboration between government institutions, businesses, and local communities.

Public engagement: Public engagement and awareness are also key challenges. Strengthening community involvement through public-private partnerships and incentives for private green initiatives could improve the effectiveness of adaptation strategies (REGKLAM, 2013).

3. Inception Workshops

3.1 Overall approach

Adaptation AGORA identified four key pilot regions in which ensuring a broad involvement of the communities to analyse relevant data and to monitor local climate change and vulnerabilities, starting with Inception Workshops (IWs). In order to start the activities, five IWs have been organized at the end of the year 2023. These workshops were face-to-face meetings organised to identify vulnerability pitfalls and gaps in their adaptive capacity through climate vulnerability assessments, bringing adaptation needs and priorities in line with the needs of local communities (soft adaptation measure). During the IWs, the participants engaged in different activities aimed at clarifying project objectives, identifying challenges and opportunities, and outlining the steps needed to move forward effectively.

The IWs were organized in Malmö, Zaragoza and Valderrobres (Aragón Region), Rome, and Dresden. They were all joined by academic representatives, policy-makers and local communities (in the form of citizens or associations), so the outcomes can represent a wide range of population with different points of view. After each workshop a final report was prepared (Annexes) collecting the main information of the meeting and the outcomes. Even though the main objective of the IWs was the same, different methodologies were adopted and different topics were addressed (sections 3.2, 3.3). The workshops in Zaragoza, Rome and Dresden widely addressed climate change without posing any limit to the audience while the meeting in Malmö was specifically focused on adaptation to heatwaves, and the meeting in Valderrobres (Aragón) was focused on forest management and fire prevention. The next table reports dates and number of participants of each IW.

Date	Location	Participants
12 September 2023	Malmö	11
24 October 2023	Zaragoza - Aragón Region	18

9 November 2023	Rome	34
16 November 2023	Dresden	24
19 December 2023	Valderrobres - Aragón Region	8

3.2 Workshop details

3.2.1 Inception Workshop in Sweden “How Can Malmö Adapt to a Changing Climate?”

General info

Where: University of Malmö

When: 12 September 2023

Participants: 11

Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
[TG2] Academia	Climate adaptation and social vulnerability, specifically focusing on heatwaves in Malmö.

<p>[TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities</p> <p>[TG4] Civil Society</p> <p>[TG6] Private sector</p> <p>[TG8] Consortium Partners</p>	<p>The goal was to lay the groundwork for future collaboration and identify key issues related to heatwave impacts and vulnerable groups.</p>
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3.2.2 First Inception Workshop in Spain “Exploring Adaptation to Climate Change in Aragon”

General info	
<p>Región de Aragón</p> <p>HOY → Primer taller de inicio en Zaragoza</p> <p>Serie de talleres a lo largo de 2024 y 2025</p> <p>↓</p> <p>FINAL: Cocreación de soluciones de adaptación al cambio climático</p> <p>Where: Aquarium of Zaragoza</p> <p>When: 24 October 2023</p> <p>Participants: 18</p>	
Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
<p>[TG2] Researchers and experts</p> <p>[TG3] Political groups</p> <p>[TG4] Environmental groups</p> <p>[TG5] Citizens</p> <p>[TG6] Private sector</p>	<p>Adaptation to climate change in Aragon region. Development of participatory dynamics and tools, promoting the sharing of ideas, values, emotions and opinions.</p>

Participatory methodologies to identify existing gaps in the region's adaptive capacity.

3.2.3 Second Inception Workshop in Spain “Working on the co-management of forests in the Matarraña and Bajo Aragón regions: Exploring adaptation to climate change”

General info

Where: Headquarters of the Matarraña region in Valderrobres (Teruel)

When: 19 December 2023

Participants: 8

Stakeholders

Main objective(s)

[TG2] Academy
 [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers
 [TG5] Citizens

Development of collaborative strategies for the sustainable management and protection of private and municipal forests in the Matarraña region, focusing on fire prevention and the conservation of natural resources in the context of climate change.

3.2.4 Inception Workshop in Italy “Inception Workshop, Roma”

General info

Where: “Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti”, Rome

When: 9 November 2023

Participants: 34

Stakeholders	Main objective(s)
[TG2] Academia [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities [TG4] Civil Society [TG6] Investors / Private Sector [TG8] Consortium Partners	Discussion about adaptation to the expected impacts of climate change in relation to a plurality of sectors identified among the key areas most vulnerable identified in the process of the preparation of Climate Change Adaptation Strategy. Definition of the main socio-economic, structural, and environmental vulnerabilities and the main

needs and criticalities of the territory's adaptive capacity.

3.2.5 Inception Workshop in Germany “AGORA - Inception Workshop in Dresden”

General info

Where: citizens' lab (Bürgerlabor), Dresden

When: 16 November 2023

Participants: 24

Stakeholders

Main objective(s)

<p>[TG2] Academia [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities [TG4] Civil Society [TG6] Investors / Private Sector</p>	<p>Identification of vulnerability and risk drivers and gaps in relation to local adaptive capacity through an assessment of local susceptibilities to the expected climate hazards. Alignment of adaptation priorities and requirements with the needs of local communities (soft adaptation measure).</p>
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3.3 Methods used

During the IWs, several techniques were used to let participants more active and foster in-depth discussions. Participatory approaches, structured activities, and visual tools were used to help the work in groups and let participants to a collaborative problem-solving. Participants were initially divided into groups to focus on topics like heatwaves, heavy rainfalls, most impacted sectors, social vulnerability, and climate adaptation. In this way they were forced to a variety of perspectives and stimulating interdisciplinary dialogue. Facilitators guided the groups through all the activities, always keeping the focus on the objectives. Each group worked to identify vulnerabilities and assess local adaptive capacity, encouraging cross-sectoral collaboration among experts from different fields. At the end of each session, there was a dynamic feedback phase where groups shared their findings with all participants. It wasn't just about summarizing discoveries but also a collective reflection that sparked new connections and opportunities for collaboration. This process not only consolidated the insights but also created a shared sense of responsibility among all participants.

Here's a summary of how the workshops were structured:

Malmö, Sweden

The workshop started with a short presentation by the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) to set the scene. The presentation introduced the Adaptation AGORA project and the EU Mission on Adaptation.

Next, the participants were divided into three smaller groups to discuss the meaning of heatwaves, climate adaptation, and social vulnerability, drawing on their diverse backgrounds and expertise. This exercise aimed at creating a shared understanding of these key concepts in an inclusive and collaborative environment, and thereby establish a solid foundation for future collaboration. Dividing into smaller groups allowed all participants to contribute meaningfully. The discussion began in an open format, with participants sharing their perspectives, while collective notes were recorded on a flipchart. Official definitions were then introduced to prompt further reflection.

The second part of the workshop focused on why certain groups are more vulnerable to heatwaves than others. In three smaller groups, participants began the discussion with an open brainstorming

session, during which they identified key factors determining vulnerability while collective notes were recorded on a flipchart. Participants then reviewed a survey of vulnerable groups identified in academic literature on heatwaves and reflected on which groups they considered most at risk in a Swedish context. The survey listed different groups, where participants ranked their vulnerability using a four-point Likert scale. This survey served as a basis for discussion and collaboration, and it was completed by the group as a whole. This process sparked deeper conversations, introducing new perspectives and insights.

In brief:

- Frontal presentation to explain the project and the rules of the workshop
- First exercise and breakout group discussions in which participants discussed the concepts of heatwave, adaptation, and social vulnerability
- Second exercise and breakout group discussions in which participants co-explored what makes certain groups more vulnerable to heatwaves than others
- Full group discussion, feedback and next steps

Zaragoza - Aragón Region, Spain

The event was structured into three main phases. It began with a series of short presentations from institutional actors sharing experiences in participatory innovation and adaptation. This was followed by co-creation sessions in four parallel working groups, where participants examined proposed adaptation measures derived from earlier focus groups. Each group assessed the feasibility, barriers, and potential of the solutions, and used a visual tool to indicate the relevance of communication and education in each case. Finally, a simple voting process was used to collectively prioritise the most relevant strategies across all groups.

In brief:

- Frontal presentation to explain the project
- Explanation of the first activity about impacts diagnosis
- Division of participants into different debate groups, with a diverse stakeholder group representation in each one
- Presentation of the outcomes
- Second activity about prioritization
- Third activity about SWOT analysis
- Full group discussion and feedback

Valderrobres - Aragón Region, Spain

A long introduction was followed by an interactive discussion between the stakeholders to identify challenges.

In brief:

- Frontal presentations by local authority

- Group discussion

Rome, Italy

The workshop began with an introduction to Rome's developing Adaptation Strategy, presented by Edoardo Zanchini (Climate Office, Municipality of Rome), linking the Adaptation AGORA Pilot to the city's adaptation activities. Paola Mercogliano (Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici - CMCC) then outlined the Adaptation AGORA project, emphasizing its goals of engaging citizens in adaptation processes, identifying vulnerabilities, defining adaptive capacity needs, and combating climate misinformation.

The session continued with an explanation of the workshop's activities, including definitions, materials, and the process behind group division. Participants focused on identifying vulnerabilities in various sectors (water, urban settlements, health, agriculture, etc.) and the local adaptation capacity needs for each sector. Five BoGs were formed, with diverse members to foster cross-disciplinary dialogue. Each group worked on infographics to identify vulnerabilities and criticalities, guided by CMCC facilitators.

After group discussions, each BoG shared their findings, with some groups selecting additional spokespeople for specific details. The workshop concluded with participants engaging in feedback and networking sessions, where they visited other groups' work and discussed potential collaborations. The session ended with thanks and a commitment to share workshop results via email, encouraging participants to stay updated through the project's social media and website. Many stakeholders expressed interest in future Adaptation AGORA developments and continued involvement in the project.

In brief:

- Frontal presentations by local authority, project leader and experts
- Division into working groups and discussion
- Groups feedback and next steps

Dresden, Germany

After a brief introduction of the Adaptation AGORA project by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), including the project's objectives and the workshop's goals, participants worked in groups to analyse how Dresden is affected by climate change, particularly in relation to heatwaves and heavy rainfall. They examined which sectors and population groups are most vulnerable to these extreme events and identified key adaptation gaps among stakeholders and citizens. This shared understanding allowed them to assess the city's existing adaptation efforts, which were presented by the Environmental Office of the City of Dresden. Participants then exchanged experiences, discussing their ongoing and future initiatives, as well as the challenges they face in climate adaptation. The workshop concluded with a focus on ECSA's next steps, emphasizing the stakeholders' commitment to maintaining the adaptation network in the long term.

In brief:

- Frontal presentation by ECSA to explain the context and the workshop
- Brainstorming session to co-explore context and priorities
- Frontal presentations by the local authority and experts
- Exchange and feedback from participants on their own measures and challenges in their sector with regard to climate adaptation
- Conclusions with stakeholder expectations and ECSA's next steps
- Feedback and networking dinner

4. Results: Updating vulnerability assessments in the pilot regions

4.1 Pilot Malmö, Sweden

The workshop (details in Annex 1) aimed to engage stakeholders in discussing climate adaptation and social vulnerability, specifically focusing on heatwaves in Malmö. The goal was to lay the groundwork for future collaboration and identify key issues related to heatwave impacts and vulnerable groups.

Findings

Emerging findings highlighted gaps in adaptive capacity related to knowledge, socioeconomic inequalities, injustices in heat exposure, legal barriers, lack of social support, marginalization, and physiological factors. Identified gaps included lack of knowledge about coping with extreme heat, socioeconomic disparities affecting adaptation measures, injustices in heat exposure based on income and location, legal barriers in regulation, lack of social support during extreme weather events, marginalization of specific groups, and physiological factors influencing coping abilities.

In particular, the Swedish population struggles with extreme heat, but migrants from warmer countries could offer valuable insights. Lower-income individuals, despite lower emissions, often live in hotter urban areas and are excluded from cool public spaces, while wealthier households reside in cooler coastal areas. Some individuals lack networks to assist them during extreme weather especially the elderly, and those with physical limitations affecting their ability to cope with heat. Moreover, there are no regulations for maximum indoor temperatures or safe working conditions during heatwaves.

Outputs

A heat wave was generally understood as a period when temperatures are excessively high for an extended duration. However, what qualifies as "too hot for too long" varies globally, influencing how different populations cope. For instance, Swedes tend to have a lower tolerance for heat compared to other regions. Climate adaptation is felt as developing a society capable of adjusting to evolving climate conditions and necessary from the global to the local level in multiple sectors.

Participants emphasized that heat waves impact people differently depending on their circumstances. Vulnerability is a complex, dynamic concept shaped by multiple interacting factors rather than being an inherent characteristic of specific groups. Some individuals who are considered vulnerable in everyday situations may not be during extreme climate events, and vice versa. Therefore, rather than labelling certain groups as permanently vulnerable, it is more constructive to analyse the social conditions that create vulnerability.

Participants also examined factors that increase susceptibility to heat waves, such as health, age, financial stability, knowledge, housing conditions, employment, social networks, and mobility. They stressed the importance of an intersectional perspective, recognizing that vulnerabilities often overlap and reinforce each other.

Reflections

The Adaptation AGORA project offers a valuable opportunity to deepen our understanding of heatwave impacts and the associated adaptation needs, capacities, and responses within a Swedish city. The workshop highlighted the importance of involving citizens and diverse stakeholders in climate adaptation efforts. We look forward to ongoing collaboration with the City of Malmö and other regional and local partners in the years ahead.

Feedback

Additionally, participants highlighted the need to identify those who might be overlooked in conventional urban planning. Homeless individuals, for example, are often disregarded despite their extensive knowledge of public spaces.

Finally, the discussion underscored the importance of a systems-based approach to problem-solving. Addressing heat waves should go beyond isolated solutions to avoid unintended consequences (maladaptation) and instead generate multiple co-benefits. For instance, integrating green infrastructure can simultaneously mitigate UHI, manage flood risks, and improve equitable access to public green spaces.

Next steps

After the IW, SEI continued its collaboration with the City of Malmö. The results from the IW informed the following pilot activities, aimed at further exploring factors contributing to urban heat vulnerability. Six months after the IW, a second workshop was organized to co-create adaptation solutions for a heat-resilient city. In addition, four focus group discussions were conducted with youth, workers, and multicultural communities. A door-to-door campaign in Rosengård engaged 100 residents in an urban heat vulnerability assessment. The findings were presented at a final co-creation event focusing on identifying soft adaptation solutions addressing urban heat vulnerability. Moving forward, the work will continue through the Formas-funded project HeatSafe, in partnership with SEI, Linköping University, the City of Malmö, and the Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3) as part of the IMAGINE Adaptation project. HeatSafe will include a citizen science campaign aimed

at enhancing the understanding of urban heat vulnerability while also strengthening public participation in climate adaptation.

4.2 Pilot Aragón, Spain

Findings

The Spanish pilot conducted two workshops—one in Zaragoza (urban) and another in a rural area—revealing significant differences in social structures and needs. Key challenges identified include low public awareness, unequal access to information and financial resources, and a stark urban-rural divide, with Aragón having one of the widest in Spain. Additional concerns include water vulnerability, lack of political commitment to environmental management, and difficulties in intervention due to urban planning constraints.

In the rural area, land ownership poses a major challenge, as much of the land is privately owned, often by absentee owners, making forest management and prevention efforts difficult. The loss of traditional ways of life and an aging, poorly connected population further hinder engagement, making adaptation efforts more complex.

Output

During the IW in Zaragoza, participants identified three key themes: environment, society, and economy. Environmental concerns included rising temperatures, water pollution, desertification, and extreme weather. Social issues focused on worsening health, inequality, energy poverty, social conflicts, and misinformation. Economic concerns involved invasive species, shifts in productive activities, food insecurity, rising energy consumption, and infrastructure damage from extreme weather.

Discussions delved deeper into social inequality, desertification, water poverty, and the impact of climate change on health. Social inequality was linked to low awareness, urban-rural disparities, and an ageing population, though Aragón benefits from youth mobilization and strong social services. Desertification was recognized as a major risk due to strong winds and a semi-arid climate, but industries are adapting, and research into alternative resources is ongoing. Water poverty emerged as a pressing issue, with water vulnerability and a lack of political commitment posing challenges, although the region has a robust hydraulic infrastructure and public awareness of water conservation. Climate change's impact on health was also a major concern, as overcrowded cities, limited green spaces, and underfunded rural services create vulnerabilities. However, Aragón benefits from access to natural areas, ongoing medical research, and a strong healthcare system.

Reflections

By identifying vulnerabilities and climate impacts in Aragón, Adaptation AGORA can better tailor its actions to local needs. The discussions highlighted both challenges and opportunities for adaptation,

revealing that, beyond heat waves and floods, participants were also deeply concerned about water scarcity and desertification. Effective dissemination and engagement strategies are crucial, especially in rural areas, to better involve the local population. Additionally, small landowner associations play a key role in forest management, and increasing their participation could greatly enhance climate adaptation efforts.

These workshops clearly demonstrated the value of soft adaptation measures rooted in local realities and stakeholder knowledge, reinforcing Adaptation AGORA's commitment to inclusive resilience planning.

Feedback

Overall, the methodology proved effective in fostering inclusive dialogue, even under constraints. Participants appreciated the interactive format in Zaragoza, particularly the SWOT analysis for its ability to identify actionable strengths and weaknesses. However, some challenges were noted:

- In Zaragoza, more time could have allowed deeper exploration of each topic.
- In Valderrobres, low attendance and time overruns required improvisation but still resulted in a productive exchange.

A key lesson is the need to adapt engagement strategies to the local context: in urban areas, structured formats and diversified group work flourish; in rural areas, flexibility, trust-building, and stronger outreach mechanisms are essential.

Next steps

The insights from both workshops will directly inform the development of Adaptation AGORA's pilot interventions. In Zaragoza, the outputs will guide the design of localized adaptation actions, particularly addressing health impacts, water issues, and social disparities. The identification of adaptive strengths also opens pathways for leveraging existing community assets.

In Valderrobres, the next phase will focus on increasing community participation, fostering associations among landowners, and supporting collaboration with forest technicians. The need for new communication and engagement strategies is evident and will be prioritized.

Future workshops in the region will build on these learnings, ensuring that each pilot is grounded in genuine local priorities, while also reinforcing cross-regional knowledge sharing within the broader Adaptation AGORA framework.

4.3 Pilot Roma, Italy

Findings

The Italian IW for the Adaptation AGORA project focused on supporting Rome's Climate Change Adaptation Strategy. Discussions centered on identifying sectoral vulnerabilities, including water,

health, biodiversity, infrastructure, and cultural heritage. Key issues identified included governance gaps, fragmented coordination, and limited access to shared information. Additionally, participants highlighted social vulnerabilities and the uneven distribution of resilience across communities, emphasizing where soft adaptation measures could be most impactful.

Outputs

The main tangible outcomes were collaboratively developed infographics that mapped sectoral vulnerabilities and adaptation priorities. These visual tools used a colour-coded system to distinguish between sector-specific and cross-sectoral challenges. The materials now serve as a foundational resource for the next phases of Rome's adaptation planning.

Reflections

The workshop reinforced the value of inclusive and co-creative approaches to vulnerability assessment. It demonstrated how tailored engagement methods bring local perspectives into climate strategy development. Furthermore, it clarified how soft adaptation measures—such as awareness-raising, capacity-building, and governance improvements—can be tailored to Rome's institutional and social context.

Feedback

Participants provided overwhelmingly positive feedback. The structured format, visual materials, and guided discussions helped organize complex information and ensure meaningful contributions. The final session, where groups reviewed each other's work, effectively encouraged cross-sectoral dialogue and even facilitated new professional connections. Several attendees noted that they had not previously interacted, despite working in overlapping fields.

Next Steps

Insights from this workshop will guide the development of Rome's adaptation strategy and contribute to the broader Adaptation AGORA project across other pilot cities. The participatory format and tools have proven effective and scalable, offering a model for future workshops. The next steps include refining the strategy based on this initial input, strengthening engagement with local stakeholders, and ensuring that identified vulnerabilities are addressed in a coherent and practical way.

4.4 Pilot Dresden, Germany

Findings

The discussions revealed a nuanced picture of Dresden's vulnerability to two key climate hazards: heatwaves and heavy rainfall/flooding. Participants conducted a problem tree analysis to explore impacts across various sectors, identifying both exposed population groups and structural

weaknesses. For heatwaves, students were noted as particularly vulnerable due to overheated school environments, while the elderly, infants, outdoor workers, and low-income groups were identified as facing elevated health risks. Social isolation, inadequate housing conditions, and the UHI effect were recurring themes. Challenges also extended to mobility, tourism, agriculture, and public space use. In the case of heavy rainfall and flooding, vulnerabilities emerged in housing, mobility, health, education, and urban infrastructure. Flood-prone zones, ageing buildings, and emergency response constraints were highlighted, alongside disruptions in education and workplace activity. The psychological toll—including fear, anxiety, and isolation—added further depth to the vulnerability profile. Beyond the sectoral impacts, participants explored adaptive capacity gaps. A lack of awareness (particularly regarding heavy rainfall), absence of tailored early warning systems, insufficient funding mechanisms, and institutional hurdles in making adaptation a mandatory administrative priority were all raised. Both thematic areas highlighted the need for stronger communication, clearer roles, greater empowerment, and better integration of citizen expertise.

Outputs

The workshop produced several practical and conceptual outputs. Through a mix of brainstorming, problem tree analysis, and open dialogue, participants collaboratively identified climate risks, affected groups, and capacity gaps. These insights were synthesised into clear categories, forming the basis for future focus groups, engagement activities, and tailored soft adaptation measures. Participants also mapped existing and planned adaptation activities—from greening urban spaces and developing heat protection plans to educational initiatives and citizen engagement tools such as the Cleema app and the Smart City Model. The city’s soon-to-be-published adaptation strategy (2024) served as an anchor point, with key action areas—health, water, and urban greenery—offering a framework for further alignment and stakeholder collaboration.

Reflections

The workshop helped surface not only existing climate risks but also how those risks intersect with local socio-economic realities. A critical reflection was the mismatch between the urgency of climate threats and the current state of preparedness, especially in governance and policy alignment. Participants recognised that soft adaptation measures—such as knowledge-sharing, community empowerment, and behavioural change—are just as important as infrastructure investments. The participatory design of the workshop enabled voices from across society to be heard, building trust and a sense of shared purpose. It also highlighted the necessity of building adaptive capacity not just through information, but through enabling environments—spaces where citizens, experts, and institutions can jointly identify problems and co-develop solutions.

Feedback

Participants appreciated the collaborative format, interactive tools, and inclusive setting. The Citizens’ Lab was viewed as a fitting and symbolic venue that encouraged openness and dialogue.

Stakeholders valued the mix of technical input (such as the city’s climate strategy) and practical group exercises, and especially the opportunity to connect across sectors. Feedback underscored a desire for continuity, with participants stressing the importance of keeping the adaptation network active beyond one-off events. Many called for greater transparency, consistent communication, and real pathways for citizens to influence planning and implementation. Some challenges were also noted, including difficulties in reaching marginalised groups, translating scientific knowledge into everyday language, and navigating bureaucratic hurdles for citizen-led initiatives. The limitations of project-based funding were highlighted repeatedly, with calls for more sustainable financial support structures.

Next Steps

The findings from the workshop will directly inform Adaptation AGORA’s next actions in the Dresden pilot. Specifically, these will include:

- Defining the content and structure of thematic focus groups, based on the identified vulnerabilities and capacity gaps.
- Co-designing citizen engagement methodologies, drawing on existing community initiatives and new participation formats.
- Strengthening collaboration between city departments, local stakeholders, and regional authorities to improve coordination.
- Translating insights into policy, supporting the refinement and eventual implementation of Dresden’s forthcoming adaptation strategy.
- Empowering youth and underrepresented groups, expanding climate education, and showcasing successful examples of engagement.

In parallel, the ECSA team will support local actors in building capacity, advocating for systemic changes (such as the introduction of heat action plans), and ensuring that promising ideas—such as the “Sponge City Dresden” concept—are scaled with the necessary institutional and financial backing. This workshop demonstrated not only the urgency of climate adaptation but also the potential for collective, community-driven solutions. With the foundation now laid, the Dresden pilot is well-positioned to move from dialogue to action—shaped by those who live, work, and care for the city every day.

5. Discussion and next steps

5.1 Discussion of results

5.1.1 Climate risks and vulnerability in the pilot regions

Despite geographical and climatic differences between the four pilot regions there are several common key climate change challenges. The four cities share common climate risks but experience

them in varying intensities. While Malmö faces coastal and urban flooding, Aragón struggles with drought and desertification, Rome deals with heatwaves, water scarcity, and extreme rainfall, and Dresden contends with flood risks and shifting precipitation patterns. Addressing these challenges requires a combination of green infrastructure, climate-resilient planning, and adaptive water management strategies.

All four pilots experience increasing average temperatures, with more frequent and intense heatwaves. UHI effect (due to heat waves) is a growing concern, especially in densely populated areas (notably in Malmö, Rome, and Dresden) with consequent heat-related health risks, including excess mortality, which are particularly problematic in vulnerable populations (e.g., elderly and low-income groups).

Heavy rainfall and extreme precipitation events are leading to flash floods, infrastructure damage, and overwhelmed drainage systems in Malmö, Rome, and Dresden. Storm surges and coastal flooding are specific risks for Malmö due to sea-level rise, while river flooding poses major threats in the other cities (Elbe River in Dresden, Ebro River in Aragón, Tiber River in Rome). Increased variability in precipitation (alternating dry and wet periods) is a common trend, especially in Rome and Dresden.

Aragón, Rome, and Dresden face drought risks, affecting water supply, agriculture, and biodiversity. The water management challenges are pressing, especially in Rome, where infrastructure aging and climate variability stress the supply system. Aragón, a semi-arid region, is particularly prone to desertification, making water conservation essential. Aragón also faces desertification and biodiversity loss, and forest fire risks due to rising temperatures. Agricultural impacts are pronounced in Aragón, where higher temperatures and unpredictable rainfall threaten crops and livestock.

In all cities, urban infrastructure is struggling to adapt to changing climate conditions with flooding and heat stress damaging roads, bridges, and buildings. Aragón and Dresden emphasize the need for sustainable urban planning and green infrastructure to mitigate heat and flooding risks.

5.1.2 Inception Workshops findings and results

The five Adaptation AGORA IWs were designed to engage a wide range of stakeholders, identify local vulnerabilities, assess adaptive capacities, and align adaptation priorities with community needs. These workshops adopted participatory and inclusive methods, enabling a bottom-up flow of information that recognised stakeholders as experts in their respective domains. Across all pilot regions—Malmö (Sweden), Aragón (Spain), Rome (Italy), and Dresden (Germany)—this approach fostered mutual learning, trust-building, and locally grounded dialogue.

Discussions in the workshops centred on four core themes: climate change impacts, vulnerability assessments, gaps in adaptive capacity, and potential solutions. Despite differing regional contexts, common findings emerged: a general lack of knowledge and awareness about climate risks, limited

social support mechanisms, and a shared need for clear leadership, improved communication, and more inclusive governance frameworks.

A number of adaptive capacity gaps were consistently identified: knowledge deficits, socioeconomic inequalities, infrastructure limitations, insufficient stakeholder engagement, and fragmented governance. Furthermore, climate adaptation is still often approached reactively, with short-term fixes taking precedence over long-term planning. Weak coordination across governance levels has also resulted in inconsistent policy implementation and unclear responsibilities.

From a climate impacts perspective, rising temperatures, increasing water scarcity, and extreme weather events are the most pressing concerns across the pilot areas. In cities less accustomed to extreme heat, such as Malmö and Dresden, heatwaves are already causing reduced labour productivity and exacerbating health risks. In Rome, Zaragoza, and Dresden, water dependency and stress were identified as significant vulnerabilities. These climate pressures are compounded by structural and social issues, such as ageing populations, rural depopulation, urban overcrowding, growing social and economic inequalities, and building stock poorly suited to a changing climate.

Each pilot region also presented unique features. For instance, Malmö’s workshop focused primarily on urban heat, while the workshop in Valderrobres concentrated on forest management and wildfire prevention—demonstrating how local climate priorities shape engagement. Most meetings followed a common structure: introductory presentations followed by small group discussions and plenary feedback sessions. All workshops ensured stakeholders had a central role in identifying key issues and suggesting concrete solutions.

The comparison between urban and rural areas in Aragón provided particularly valuable insights. While Zaragoza exhibited challenges typical of growing urban centres, Valderrobres highlighted the difficulty of mobilising stakeholders in rural settings—due in large part to depopulation, poor infrastructure, and an ageing population. This disparity reflects broader trends of uneven adaptive capacity, which vary considerably depending on geography, social context, and available resources.

Similarities and differences between the regions

Similarities:

- Climate risks such as heatwaves, flooding, and drought were widespread across all sites.
- Social vulnerability and inequality emerged as cross-cutting concerns, particularly affecting older people, low-income households, and marginalised communities.
- Adaptation gaps—including lack of funding, fragmented governance, and limited community engagement—were frequently cited.
- A shared recognition of the value of nature-based solutions and the need to scale them up was evident.

Differences:

- Malmö and Dresden prioritised urban adaptation challenges, particularly related to UHI effects and infrastructure stress, whereas Valderrobres focused on rural forest management and community resilience.
- Rome highlighted the interplay between climate impacts and cultural heritage, as well as hydrogeological and coastal risks.
- Aragón region underscored the impacts of desertification and agricultural vulnerability, revealing stark contrasts between urban and rural adaptation capacities.
- Engagement levels varied, with rural pilots encountering greater difficulties in participation due to demographic and geographic barriers.

5.1.3 Contextualization of pilots' results in scientific literature

Over the past decade, climate adaptation has evolved into a diverse and rapidly expanding field of research. The workshops held in Malmö, Aragón, Rome, and Dresden provide a valuable empirical complement to the existing academic literature. When examined together, they offer a rich comparative lens through which to assess the state of climate adaptation thinking and practice in Europe. While significant areas of alignment exist, the comparison of theory and practice also reveals critical gaps in policy translation, inclusivity, and implementation.

Vulnerability

The concept of vulnerability has undergone a significant transformation in academic discourse, shifting from a narrow focus on biophysical exposure to a more integrated, socially constructed understanding. Scholars such as Adger (2006) and Eriksen & O'Brien (2007) emphasise that vulnerability is shaped not only by environmental hazards but also by historical, political, and socioeconomic structures. Contemporary literature increasingly calls for intersectional and context-specific approaches that recognise how gender, age, income, and ethnicity intersect to shape climate risks (Nightingale et al., 2020).

These theoretical insights are clearly echoed in the Malmö and Dresden workshops. In Malmö, participants rejected static definitions of vulnerability, instead emphasising how it emerges from dynamic social conditions such as isolation, poor housing, and lack of support networks—particularly during heatwaves. So inequality, injustice and marginalization have a relevant impact on vulnerability. Dresden similarly highlighted groups such as students and low-income residents who face heightened exposure due to infrastructural deficits and social isolation.

The Aragón workshops, especially those in rural settings, also underlined the role of demographic and infrastructural challenges—such as depopulation, ageing, and land ownership structures—in shaping adaptive capacity. In contrast, Rome's workshop, while addressing vulnerability, was more sectoral-focused, primarily using visual tools to identify institutional and infrastructural weaknesses rather than exploring the lived experience of at-risk groups in depth.

Governance, Participation, and Institutional Gaps

The literature has long noted the uneven political prioritisation of adaptation, particularly in Europe. While the Paris Agreement and IPCC reports have increased global attention (Biesbroek et al., 2022), adaptation remains fragmented, with many countries focusing more on impact assessment than on implementation. Scholars point to the need for participatory governance, where communities play a meaningful role in shaping adaptation strategies.

Workshop findings both support and complicate this picture. In Rome and Dresden, fragmented governance structures and poor institutional coordination were highlighted as key barriers to effective adaptation. Rome's case, in particular, revealed that even where formal strategies exist, soft measures such as coordination, communication, and shared information remain underdeveloped.

The Aragón workshops notably discussed the challenges of engaging rural communities, where traditional knowledge systems are fading and political will is limited. Here, the literature's concern with the underrepresentation of vulnerable regions and populations is particularly salient.

Risk Perception, Communication, and Adaptive Responses

A recurring theme in both the literature and workshop outputs is the complexity of communicating and managing climate risk. Scholars such as Weber (2010) and Moser (2010) have shown that risk perception is shaped by trust, experience, and emotion—rather than by data alone. The literature increasingly calls for empathetic, localised communication strategies.

In the workshops, however, this modulation was not always fully addressed. While Zaragoza participants discussed misinformation and low public awareness, particularly around water and health risks, the workshops generally placed more emphasis on identifying risks than on exploring how they are perceived or communicated. The Dresden workshop briefly mentioned the psychological toll of extreme weather, including fear and anxiety, aligning with recent concerns around eco-anxiety and emotional resilience (Coffey et al., 2021). The eco-anxiety was also slightly addressed during the IW in Zaragoza but not in Rome and Malmö. Yet, the topic remains underdeveloped, with few practical mechanisms proposed for addressing climate-related stress, especially among young or marginalised groups.

Justice, Inequality, and Adaptive Capacity

Literature on climate justice and inequality has grown significantly, with mounting evidence that climate change disproportionately affects lower-income and marginalised populations (Mejean et al., 2024). Moreover, there is a growing recognition that without equitable access to resources, governance structures, and early warning systems, adaptation efforts risk deepening existing inequalities.

This concern was vividly illustrated in the Malmö workshop, where participants noted that those contributing least to emissions—such as low-income households and migrants—often suffer the most from heat exposure and are excluded from adaptive infrastructures like green spaces or

cooling centres. Similarly, in Dresden, the elderly and physically limited individuals were highlighted as being particularly vulnerable in the absence of social networks or heat-safe housing.

Yet, while the literature calls for systemic change and inclusive financial mechanisms, the workshops were more focused on identifying present-day gaps rather than proposing structural reforms. This reflects a broader disconnect between high-level academic and policy ambitions and the practical realities on the ground.

Gap Analysis

The following table summarises the key gaps identified between academic literature and empirical workshop findings:

Gap	Description
Implementation vs. Recognition	While vulnerability and justice are well-theorised in literature, many workshops stopped at identification and lacked concrete pathways for intervention or structural changes
Participation Quality	Academic discourse advocates for deep co-production of adaptation knowledge, but workshops revealed uneven and often superficial forms of public engagement
Emotional and Psychological Dimensions	Literature increasingly engages with eco-anxiety and risk perception, yet few workshops addressed these emotional aspects practically
Communication of Risk	There is a mismatch between literature’s call for empathetic communication and limited workshop discussion on public messaging
Equity in Adaptation Finance and Planning	While academic work stresses inclusive financial mechanisms, workshops rarely address this dimension
Metrics and Evaluation	Clear indicators or evaluation frameworks were largely absent in the empirical discussions

Conclusions

The convergence between academic literature and workshop insights demonstrates a growing maturity in how vulnerability, risk, and adaptation are conceptualised and discussed. However, the journey from recognition to transformation remains incomplete. While workshops offer a grounded, practice-oriented view of the challenges faced by diverse regions, they often lack the policy leverage, institutional commitment, or financial mechanisms needed to fully implement equitable and inclusive adaptation strategies. Addressing these gaps requires not only stronger alignment between academic frameworks and local realities but also political will, long-term funding, and participatory mechanisms that move beyond consultation toward genuine co-creation of adaptive futures.

5.2 Next steps

Each of the four pilot regions has planned to conduct at least three in-person focus groups with citizens and civil society, along with at least one co-creation workshop. These workshops will bring together citizens, civil society, academics, experts, and policymakers. The pilot regions have engaged identified and interested stakeholders beyond the IWs through follow-up meetings. These meetings not only helped strengthen networks but were also instrumental in mapping citizen target groups and identifying relevant institutions and potential contacts to ensure the right participants were involved in the focus groups. The outcomes of the IW sessions have contributed to other tasks aimed at co-designing and co-creating innovative soft climate adaptation solutions with local citizens and stakeholders from the four pilot regions. Based on the climate adaptation strategies identified in the IWs, activities will be tailored to each target group. These activities include a minimum of three co-design focus groups with citizens and civil society, as well as one co-creation workshop per region, engaging citizens, civil society, academics, experts, and policymakers.

Building on the insights gained from the IWs and guided by the Tandem framework for co-production and co-design, follow-up meetings have been held in the pilot regions. These meetings have reinforced local networks and enabled stakeholders to identify and prioritize adaptation challenges for the focus groups. Additionally, stakeholders have played a key role in mapping citizen target groups and identifying relevant institutions and contacts. Their involvement has ensured that their interests and priorities are reflected in defining key adaptation issues, making solutions more locally relevant and increasing the likelihood of future implementation.

So far, 17 focus groups have been conducted, emphasizing the co-design and co-creation of innovative soft climate adaptation solutions.

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7. Annexes

7.1 Annex 1 – Report Malmö Inception Workshop

Event title & rationale

AGORA Inception workshop – how can Malmö adapt to a changing climate?

SEI HQ held its first pilot activity in the city of Malmö where a wide range of stakeholders were invited to discuss climate adaptation and social vulnerability. The aim was to spark an interest among stakeholders and thereby create a solid foundation for future collaboration. The workshop focused specifically on adaptation to heatwaves in Malmö and explored who is affected and why, taking into consideration both social and physical factors.

Date, Time and Location

12th of September 2023, Malmö University.

Agenda

Introduction and project presentation

Exercise 1 – what do we mean?

Breakout group discussions in which participants discussed the concepts of heatwave, adaptation, and social vulnerability.

Exercise 2 – who is impacted?

Breakout group discussion in which participants co-explored what makes certain groups more vulnerable to heatwaves than others.

Full-group discussion

Feedback and next steps

Number of participants, including from which Target Group

11 participants from the City of Malmö.

Executive summary

The workshop started with a short presentation to set the scene and introduce participants to the Adaptation AGORA project and how it is related to climate adaptation and heat mitigation in Malmö as well as clarify the “rules of the game” and workshop set-up. Next, three smaller groups were formed (spreading the various backgrounds as evenly as possible) to discuss the terms heatwave, social vulnerability and climate adaptation and determine whether there were any differing

understandings of these concepts. Participants took notes on flipcharts, one per group. Next, a second break-out discussion was conducted but based on the questions of who they considered to be the most affected in periods of extreme heat, how they are affected, and why. The participants were prompted to discuss this based on their understanding of the terms from the previous discussion and their respective professional backgrounds and expertise. After some time, they were provided with an extensive list of groups identified in the academic literature as being vulnerable to heatwaves in a European and North American context. Participants discussed the various groups depending on their perceived level of vulnerability to facilitate a discussion on why certain groups might be more vulnerable than others.

Gaps in adaptive capacity of citizens and stakeholders

We consider adaptive capacity as the physical, social, economic, environmental, and institutional factors or processes that increase the ability of an individual or group to adjust to climate change and its impacts.

Although focusing on social vulnerability, various gaps in adaptive capacity were identified in the workshop. Below we summarize some emerging findings that we aim to follow-up in the next project phase:

- Lack of knowledge

Coping with extreme heat remains a challenge for the Swedish population as it is accustomed to a cooler climate. This creates an opportunity to learn from migrants from warmer countries, who possess valuable insights on effectively dealing with heatwaves.

- Socioeconomic inequalities

In Malmö, socioeconomic disparities are evident. Certain residents lack the financial means to invest in adaptation measures like summer houses, gardens, or air conditioning.

- Injustices in heat exposure

A notable inequity arises as lower-income individuals, who contribute less to climate change as they have lower consumption-based emissions, often find themselves residing in areas more susceptible to UHI. In contrast, wealthier households, with higher consumption-based emissions, tend to reside in areas close to the coast.

- Legal barriers

The absence of adequate legislation hinders adaptive capacity. For example, while there are national regulations stipulating minimum temperatures in homes during colder winter months, no equivalent regulation exists to address maximum temperatures during heatwaves. Furthermore, there are no regulations for ensuring safe work environments during heatwaves.

- Lack of social support

Some segments of the population lack support networks during heatwaves or other extreme weather events. They often face isolation, with no one to check on their well-being.

- Marginalization

Social norms contribute to the marginalization of specific groups, further diminishing their adaptive capacity. For instance, individuals experiencing homelessness are often denied access to public cool spaces such as malls, museums, or libraries.

- Physiological factors

Physiological factors play a significant role in shaping adaptive capacity. High age, preexisting medical conditions, and physical limitations influence the ability to cope with extreme heat.

Key takeaways from each activity

Exercise 1 – what do we mean?

Participants discussed how to define heat waves, climate adaptation, and social vulnerability.

A heat wave was understood as when it is too hot for too long. But when is it too hot for too long? There are differences around the world that affect how well we cope with heatwaves - Swedes have a low threshold.

According to the participants, climate adaptation means building a society that can adapt to new and changing climate conditions. Climate adaptation is needed at all scales - from the global to the local - and includes a range of sectors such as cities, land use, agriculture, livelihoods, and the work environment.

The participants said that social vulnerability produces differentiated impacts of a heatwave. Social vulnerability is a complex issue; everyone has vulnerabilities, skills, and capacities to cope with heat. It often involves several interacting factors. People who are considered vulnerable under normal conditions might not be vulnerable during extreme climate events and vice versa. Vulnerability is something that is created socially, and one should therefore think in terms of what creates vulnerabilities instead of seeing certain social groups as chronically vulnerable.

Exercise 2 – who is impacted?

Participants discussed factors that make some groups more vulnerable to heatwaves than others. According to the participants, several factors affect vulnerability – such as health, age, knowledge, financial resources, housing, employment and occupation, social networks, and mobility. Participants emphasized the importance of adopting an intersectional approach to social vulnerability as factors can reinforce one another. For example, elderly might not be vulnerable per se unless also having few social connections and mobility issues due to bad health.

Participants also emphasized that it is important to analyse who risks being left behind in conventional urban planning. For example, homeless people tend to be neglected in urban planning despite having a strong understanding of public spaces.

Lastly, the participants stressed the need for approaching problems and identifying solutions from a systems perspective to avoid maladaptation and achieving multiple co-benefits, for example using

green infrastructure solutions to tackle both UHI, flood management, and equitable access to green public spaces.

Conclusion and next steps

The results from the IW will be used as a basis for continued studies of social vulnerability to heatwaves in Malmö. In the next pilot phase, the project team will interview citizens to gain a deeper understanding of their experiences of, and capacities to cope with, heatwaves. The insights from these interviews will also inform City of Malmö's work on assessing social vulnerability to heatwaves that recently was initiated as part of the Adaptation AGORA project.

The Adaptation AGORA project presents a unique opportunity to enhance our understanding of the impacts of heatwaves and related adaptation needs, capacities and responses in the context of a Swedish city. Overall, the workshop underscored the potential of engaging citizens and a wide range of actors in climate adaptation discussions, and we look forward to continued collaboration with City of Malmö and other regional and local stakeholders in the coming years.

7.2 Annex 2 – Report Zaragoza Inception Workshop

Event title & rationale

Participatory workshop: Exploring adaptation to climate change in Aragón.

General objective of the workshop: Description of the climate change impacts in the region of Aragón.

Specific objectives of the workshop:

- Explore the economic, social, and environmental consequences of climate change in the region of Aragón.
- Identify the region's needs for enhanced climate adaptation.

Date, Time and Location

24th October 2023 17:00 - 18:55, Aquarium of Zaragoza.

Agenda

Welcome (5 minutes)

Agora's presentation (5 minutes)

First activity: Impacts diagnosis (23 minutes) and Explanation of the exercise (3 minutes)

Division of participants into different debate groups, with a diverse stakeholder group representation in each one. On each table there was a flipchart with post-its, divided by the areas that we want to study (economic, environmental, social) drawn on the flipchart. Time: 20 minutes.

Oral presentations. Brief explanation about what has been noted and discussed in each group. Time: 10 minutes.

Second activity: Prioritization

Participants select which are the 4 most important topics / impacts. Time: 10 minutes.

Third activity: SWOT

The same number of flip charts are distributed in SWOT format with different post-its available. Each SWOT is made around each topic prioritized previously. Time: 30 minutes

Oral presentations. Brief explanation about what has been noted and discussed in each group. Time: 15 minutes.

Closing (5 minutes)

Number of participants, including from which Target Group

18 participants

- [TG2] Researchers and experts: 7 participants
- [TG3] Political groups: 4 participants
- [TG4] Environmental groups: 4 participants
- [TG5] Citizens: 1 participant
- [TG6] Private sector: 2 participants

Executive summary

The workshop explored the situation of the Aragon region in the fight against climate change through the development of participatory dynamics and tools, promoting the sharing of ideas, values, emotions and opinions among the participants.

The use of participatory methodologies facilitated discussions among participants, allowing the Adaptation AGORA team to identify existing gaps in the region's adaptive capacity, which will be addressed in the next steps of the project.

Gaps in adaptive capacity of citizens and stakeholders

Several gaps in the region's adaptive capacity were identified thanks to the debates generated in the workshop. Some of the most important were:

- the lack of social awareness;
- unequal access to informative and economic resources;
- the unequal distribution between the urban and rural population, Aragon being one of the communities with the highest urban-rural gap in Spain;
- the aging of the population.

Other relevant gaps that were noted were hydric vulnerability and the lack of political commitment in the management of water and environment. Additionally, there is a concentration of vulnerable populations in certain zones, which makes intervention in these areas challenging due to urban planning characteristics.

Key takeaways from each activity

The first activity was aimed at identifying the impacts of climate change in the Aragon region through the question: Which are the most relevant impacts that you are concerned about or that you are aware of in the Aragon region? Due to the fact that the impacts were previously divided into environmental, social and economic ones, it was possible to debate on a more concrete scale.

At the environmental level, the increase in temperature, water pollution and its loss of quality, desertification and extreme events were identified in all discussion groups. Other outputs from the different groups were: water poverty, loss of biodiversity, atmospheric pollution, loss of soil and air quality, and forest and electrical fires.

At the social level, the worsening of physical and mental health (with a special emphasis on the 'eco-anxiety' concept), the increase in inequality and energy poverty, the intensification of coexistence conflicts, heat islands in urban areas, depopulation and misinformation were noted.

At the economic level, the groups identified the invasion of exotic species and the increase in pests, the changes in productive activity, the loss of agricultural production and its consequent food insecurity and increasing food prices. Also, the increase in energy consumption due to heat waves and the damage to infrastructure due to extreme weather events were mentioned.

In the second activity, attendees prioritized four topics to discuss in the third activity. The topics were: the impact of climate change on health, desertification, water poverty and social inequality.

In the third activity, the four chosen topics were randomly assigned to the four discussion groups and the adaptive gaps were identified through a SWOT analysis.

In regards to social inequality, the main weaknesses identified were the lack of social awareness, the unequal distribution between the urban and rural population, and the aging of the population, which implies loneliness and technological gap. The strengths of Aragon's territory in the adaptive process were also highlighted, including its capacity for youth mobilization, the presence of neighborhood and support networks, robust social services, and a well-functioning public health system.

Secondly, regarding desertification, the weaknesses identified were the characteristic meteorological phenomena of Aragon, such as the wind and the resulting erosion, as well as the semi-arid climate that is typical of the region. The discussion group pointed out as strengths the industry already adapted to historical water poverty and the already existing research on the alternative uses of existing natural resources.

Thirdly, the main weaknesses that the Aragon region faces regarding water poverty is water vulnerability and the lack of political commitment in the water and environment management - some participants expressed concerns about large-scale ski resort expansion projects in the Aragonese Pyrenees-. As for strengths, the participants discussed the robust hydraulic infrastructure, public awareness of water conservation, and ongoing R&D projects.

Finally, regarding the impact of climate change on our health, concerns were raised about the aging of the population, the overcrowding of cities, the neglect of public services in rural areas, the few existing green spaces and the concentration of population. The region's strengths include the existence of large rivers - the Ebro River in this case -, the large nearby natural spaces, ongoing medical research and prevention plans, as well as the reiteration of the value of public health.

Conclusion and next steps

The results will be analyzed and used for the continuation of Adaptation AGORA. Thanks to the identification of vulnerabilities and impacts in the Aragon region, Adaptation AGORA actions can be applied more effectively. Not only have the challenges and threats implied by climate change in the region been identified, but the strengths and opportunities for adaptation and mitigation of negative effects have also been discussed. We obtained insightful and enriching results about the challenges and unique characteristics of the Aragon region. While our earlier meetings with representatives of the Government of Aragon led us to believe that the primary concerns were heat waves and floods, this workshop has revealed that participants were also worried about issues like water scarcity and desertification.

Furthermore, in the month of November another first workshop will be held in the Matarraña region (rural area), the second Adaptation AGORA pilot in Spain, also aimed at identifying the vulnerabilities and impacts that climate change has on that particular geographical area and its population.

7.3 Annex 3 – Report Matarraña Inception Workshop

Event title & rationale

Working on the co-management of forests in the Matarraña and Bajo Aragón regions: Exploring adaptation to climate change

General objective of the workshop: : Develop collaborative strategies for the sustainable management and protection of private and municipal forests in the Matarraña region, focusing on fire prevention and the conservation of natural resources in the context of climate change.

Specific objectives of the workshop:

Raise awareness about the importance of active and sustainable management of private forests to prevent fires and conserve ecosystems.

Identify resources and supports available to improve community knowledge to prevent and respond to wildfires.

Encourage the formation of associations among private landowners to facilitate the collective and efficient management of forests.

Explore opportunities to collaborate with forestry agents and other professionals in the protection and conservation of forests.

Date, Time and Location

19th of December 2023 17:30 – 19:30, Valderrobres (Teruel) Headquarters of the Matarraña region.

Agenda

Welcome (5 minutes)

Context. Time: 35 minutes

Agora and Decido presentation (10 minutes)

Forest Technician explains the environmental situation of the region (10 minutes)

Environmental group explains their initiative to improve forest management (10 minutes)

Questions and comments (5 minutes)

Pause (10 minutes)

Activity: Working groups. Time: 1h 05min

Division of participants into two groups, with a diverse stakeholder group representation in each one. On each table there was a flipchart divided by different questions that lead into debate, so participants can write down conclusions and comments (50 minutes)

Oral presentations. Brief explanation about what has been noted and discussed in each group. Time: 15 minutes.

Closing and feedback (5 minutes)

Number of participants, including from which Target Group

8 Participants

- [TG2] Academy: 3 participants
- [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers: 3 participants (Matarraña region, Forest Technician and Regional Agro-environmental Office)
- [TG5] Citizens: 2 participants

Executive summary

This 2-hour workshop took place in the Matarraña region, and brought together private landowners, forestry agents, government representatives and other stakeholders. Through interactive discussions and group debates, attendees worked together to identify challenges, opportunities and strategies for sustainable forest management in the context of climate change. The workshop focused on fire prevention, the conservation of natural resources and community collaboration to protect and enhance the forest ecosystems of the region.

A mapping of essential actors and stakeholders in the area has been carried out since we are working from a distance, therefore, we consider it essential to exercise a merely facilitating and mediating function between the actors who reside and work in the territory. One of the most important missions is to make the technology and knowledge that the Adaptation AGORA project is generating available to citizens.

An important fact is that the planned agenda could not be followed due to the low attendance and the long intervention of the forestry agents (very enriching to put the workshop in context), therefore, the tables proposed for the work tables were not completed, therefore a debate was energized in relation to everything explained above.

Gaps in adaptive capacity of citizens and stakeholders

One of the most characteristic factors of this pilot is the rural and touristic environment in which it is framed, therefore it is necessary to take these characteristics into account in a transversal way when identifying adaptive gaps.

In relation to the adaptive gaps of the stakeholders that we have identified, it is the private property and smallholder ownership of the forests in the area. This affects the cleaning of the forest (by powers, by regulations, etc.). In the area there is very little public domain and there are also some areas like the municipality of La Cerollera where everything is private: in a town with about 80 inhabitants, there are about 350 owners. It is thus confirmed that in these areas the way of life of decades ago has been lost (many farmers, a lot of life in farmhouses, heating with wood from the mountains, etc.) but the type of property is maintained, with the aggravating factor that many owners are no longer in the area and are not interested in its management, making prevention work by forestry agents impossible.

On the other hand, the adaptive gaps on the part of citizens have more to do with engagement and the necessary strategies. Although we already have a community of organized citizens that has been created, we identified a great difficulty in reaching the interested population and also in arousing people's interest in such an important problem. There are many towns in the area, poorly connected and with a very aged population. It is difficult to reach the target group, since depopulation also means that many of the plot owners do not reside in the area.

Key takeaways from each activity

As already mentioned in the document, the planned agenda was not followed and finally a debate was energized in relation to everything explained above.

During the debate, great concern was detected about the lack of awareness among the population regarding the problem of forest fires and the great danger they represent for the area. Therefore, the most important need is to promote associationism on this topic in the area, since the objectives and needs are already identified. The dissemination of forestry interventions and their great capacity to prevent fires is important, as is the need to rethink engagement strategies and dissemination of the following workshops. Finally, some important stakeholders, such as the regional government or forestry agents, are very interested and willing to collaborate in whatever is necessary.

Conclusion and next steps

In conclusion, the importance of innovating in dissemination and engagement mechanisms among the population of the area is reiterated. We must learn how to intervene in rural areas just as we do in cities and how to attract the attention of the target group.

On the other hand, the association of small landowners is essential for the proper functioning of forest cleaning, therefore, by achieving an increase in participation we could advance considerably in the process.

7.4 Annex 4 – Report Rome Inception Workshop

Event title & rationale

Inception Workshop, Roma

Context and Objectives:

The Italian pilot case of the Adaptation AGORA project relates to the city of Rome. In this context, Adaptation AGORA aims to support the definition of the city's Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, currently under development. Therefore, on the 9th of November, a wide range of local stakeholders have been invited to discuss adaptation to the expected impacts of climate change in relation to a plurality of sectors (8 in total) identified among the key areas most vulnerable (and therefore under risk) identified in the process of the preparation of Climate Change Adaptation Strategy. They are:

- water (understood as management of the resource but also as impacts related to rainfall);
- urban settlements;
- networks and infrastructures;
- cultural heritage;
- health;
- socio-economic system;
- marine and coastal system;
- agricultural and livestock system;

- biodiversity and ecosystems.

The objective was to define the main socio-economic, structural, and environmental vulnerabilities as well as the main needs and criticalities pertaining to the adaptive capacity of the territory and to its citizens for each sector under investigation.

Date, Time and Location

9th of November 2023 9:30 - 13:30, Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti, Piazzale della Stazione Tiburtina, 00162 Roma

Agenda

09:30 – 09:45 Registration

09:45 – 10:30 Institutional Greetings and Introductory Session

Director of the Climate Office of the Municipality of Rome, Dr. Edoardo Zanchini.

"Towards a Climate Change Adaptation Strategy"

Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change, Head of the REgional Models and geo-Hydrological Impacts Division, Dr. Paola Mercogliano.

"The AGORA Project: Contextualisation"

10:30 – 10:45 Breakout Groups (BoGs): activity description and clarifications

Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change, PhD and research of the REgional Models and geo-Hydrological Impacts Division, Dr. Marta Ellena.

" Division into working groups and introduction to the activity "

10:45 – 11:15 Coffee Break

11:15 – 12:30 Breakout Groups (BoGs)

12:30 – 13:00 Report back from BoG (table to table)

13:00 – 13:30 Greetings and next steps

Number of participants, including from which Target Group

34 Participants

- [TG2] Academia: 8 participants
- [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities: 7 participants
- [TG4] Civil Society (which include TG1 - Local Communities): 8 participants
- [TG6] Investors / Private Sector: 7 participants
- [TG8] Consortium Partners and EC project Officers: 4 participants (APRE; CIMA; Municipality of Rome)

Executive summary

The workshop started on time with an introduction to the Adaptation Strategy currently under development, by Edoardo Zanchini (Climate Office, Municipality of Rome). This introduction was useful to allow attendees to understand the link between the Adaptation AGORA Pilot in Rome, the city's adaptation activities currently in place and how the workshop could contribute to co-design the strategy. This was followed by a presentation of the project, by Paola Mercogliano (CMCC), to highlight the main aspects of the project and to describe the activities that are being carried out in different parts of Europe in order to (i) involve citizens more closely in adaptation processes (ii) identify and determine structural, governance and social vulnerabilities, as well as (iii) define adaptive capacity needs/criticalities on the ground and, finally, (iv) disseminate the project's main objectives related to increasing climate knowledge and - implicitly - thereby decreasing climate misinformation.

After this introduction, the following session focused on explaining the activities that would be carried out during the workshop. In this regard, the definitions to base the activities on (with examples, useful as inputs for the BoGs), the materials to work with (infographics and post-its divided by colour), the schedule and allocated timeline for each activity as well as the process/reasoning behind the division of the groups. To allow elements to be easily signalled-out, "warm colours" post-its (orange, peach and yellow) were used to identify elements pertaining to a single sector (e.g., only to "water"), while the "bright colours" (green and fuchsia) were assigned to those elements which aspects could pertain to two or more sectors (e.g., to "water" and "biodiversity and ecosystems").

Participants were requested to focus on the identification of vulnerability elements per sector under analysis (water, urban settlements, networks and infrastructures, cultural heritage, health, socio-economic system, marine and coastal system, agricultural and livestock system, and biodiversity and ecosystems) and identification of needs and criticalities related to the local adaptive capacity for each of those sectors. The activities were conducted in parallel in an attempt to identify vulnerable elements and potential adaptation responses concomitantly in each case.

Five BoGs were then formed (with members from different target groups to foster an interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary dialogue on several knowledge areas. To achieve this goal, members of each BoG had at their disposal two infographics, one to identify vulnerabilities and the other to detect criticalities for local adaptive capacity where they could add their post-it's during the joint-group discussion.

The participants worked on the structured infographics and were guided by each facilitator. This role was represented by one member of the CMCC team per table. At the beginning of the work session, each group was asked to identify one person to report back at the end of the activity. Once the teams finished their discussion and identification phase, they coordinated the presentation and all members of each of the five BoGs were encouraged to add more details and support their peers.

In some instances, this resulted in participants choosing an additional spokesperson to provide more specific details on some of their findings.

The workshop finished with an overall dynamic and itinerant feedback as participants from all groups went “table-by-table” to see the results and structure of the work carried out by other BoGs, the final infographics with a complete picture of the vulnerabilities and needs for capacity building identified in each case. While hearing the report from each group, many of them were eager to engage in small conversations and establish new links with one another, identifying areas of collaboration between their organizations-. This was an additional unintended benefit from this workshop, as it created a platform and framework for discussion between stakeholders that did not know one another and had many areas in common as well as potential synergies in their professional activities.

The workshop concluded with a general thank-you, specifying how the slides as well as the results from the different working groups would be shared via e-mail to align all the participants about the work done in this first Italian inception workshop (as requested by participants). Participants were also encouraged to follow the project’s social media and website updates to learn more about the results from other workshops in Europe. Many of the stakeholders present in the Rome Pilot were interested in learning more about Adaptation AGORA’s partial results, future developments and being involved in the subsequent phases of the project.

Gaps in adaptive capacity of citizens and stakeholders

(...)

Key takeaways from each activity

1st infographic

Identification of elements of vulnerability by sector

The information collected for the vulnerability elements was categorised into elements pertaining to a single sector or elements pertaining to several sectors. For this reason, each element included in this infographic is included here under a single sector or under the section called “multisectoral”.

Water

- General Plan for Public Water Use
- Regulatory Inefficiency
- Water network leaks (40%)
- Costs associated with river flood protection
- Landslides occurrences
- Shacks near riverbanks (also related to adaptive capacity needs)
- Water supply upgrading

Biodiversity & ecosystems

- Felled trees due to pathogens
- Non-native trees (e.g. maritime pine)
- Overabundance of animal species (wild boar and blue crab)

Agricultural & livestock system

- Poor networking and involvement of local farms in urban planning in this area
- Wild boar (high percentage)
- Alien species
- Parasites
- Unsustainable food production system
- Few spatialised system data in relation to elements of these systems

Marin & coastal ecosystems

- Coastal erosion
- Use of groundwater reserves
- Adverse effects on agricultural aquaculture activities

Socioeconomic systems

- Serious effects on summer tourism (focus on summer heat)
- Limited number of staff working on these management issues (also related to adaptive capacity needs)
- Social isolation

Health

- Fragile population: chronically ill and under continuous care, children, old and very old population (over 65, 75, and 80 years old), pregnant women, migrants (i.e., languages limitation, socioeconomic rate, housing condition), and homeless.

Cultural heritage

- Spatial distribution, exposure, position (altitude) of the cultural heritage of the city of Rome
- Lack of care for heritage and millenary structures
- Outdoor cultural heritage (directly exposed to risks)
- Poor communication between the governance bodies for this sector

Network & infrastructures

- Road surface quality
- Sewerage network
- Commuting
- Inadequate urban transport
- Lack of interconnection between transports
- Bus stops in the sun

Urban settlements

- Overcrowding (i.e., population density)
- Distribution of the built environment
- Unused building abandonment
- Ineffective and outdated urban planning
- Green areas
- Squatting and unauthorised building
- Lack of services: “ghetto suburbs”
- Concentration of offices and administrative buildings
- Energy communities

Multisectoral elements

- Soil consumption (interlinked with water, agricultural & livestock system, marine and coastal ecosystems, and urban settlements)
- Water resource availability (interlinked with water, agricultural & livestock system, infrastructures, and urban settlements)
- Stress of mass tourism (interlinked with water, agricultural & livestock system, infrastructures, urban settlements, and socioeconomic system)
- Inability to absorb rainwater with hydrogeological risk zones (interlinked with water, infrastructures, and urban settlements)
- Age of the population (interlinked with urban settlements, socioeconomic system, and health) lack of impact and projection studies (across all sectors)
- Lack of stress tests (across all sectors)
- Social inequalities in general (across all sectors)
- Health care and services, including home care in general (across all sectors)
- Physical and social isolation in general (across all sectors)
- Quality of environmental matrices in general: air, water, soil (across all sectors)
- Unexploited data for economic and even natural systems (panel data from 1971 that could be useful for prevention) (across all sectors)
- Lack of data linkage between sectors (across all sectors)
- Green areas in general (across all sectors)

(*) Several of the elements included here could also be included among the needs and criticalities of adaptive capacity. However, where highlighted by the groups, this has been written down. Therefore, the elements included here were explicitly decided upon among the group stakeholders.

2nd infographic

Adaptive capacity: identification of needs and criticalities by sector

The information collected for the adaptive capacity needs and criticalities was categorised into elements pertaining to a single sector or elements pertaining to several sectors. For this reason, each element included in this infographic is included here under a single sector or under the section called “multisectoral”.

Water

- Protection and maintenance of riverbanks
- Shacks near riverbanks (also related to vulnerability)

Biodiversity & ecosystems

- Forestation of the currently most impoverished areas
- Strengthening urban gardens
- Forestation farm areas to mitigate Urban Heat Island
- Research on adaptive species

Agricultural & livestock system

- Farm involvement

Marin & coastal ecosystems

- Marine and coastal ecosystems protection
- Targeted sediment management
- Road surface maintenance and upgrading

Socioeconomic systems

- Inadequate training (with focus on young people: schools and educators)
- Social discomfort as an essential starting point for adaptation
- Limited number of staff working on these management issues (also related to vulnerability elements)
- Strengthening organisations networks already active on social issues
- Inadequate funds (focus on social work)
- Precariousness of voluntary associations, useful to inform and support the most fragile
- Tight project timeframes
- Need for tax incentives on municipal and regional taxes to be invested in adaptation plans
- Tourist tax constraint on compensation/adaptation

Health

- Lack of warning systems with priority for fragile people
- Communication campaigns per district
- Prevention of climate-related diseases (west-Nile, vector-borne diseases, etc.)
- Health facility training
- Strengthening care services

Cultural heritage

- Securing museum basements
- Risk assessment and maintenance of open-air areas
- Redevelopment of disused building stock

Network & infrastructures

- Nursery school cooling

Urban settlements

- Nursery school cooling
- Risk assessment of flattened houses
- Targeted assessment for the location of new migrant care centres (often in peripheral and poorly accessible areas)
- Urban planning that emphasises social policies
- Soil de-impermeabilisation

Multisectoral elements

- Lack of an urban reforestation plan (interlinked with water, biodiversity & ecosystems, urban settlements, health, socioeconomic systems, and cultural heritage)
- Soil consumption (interlinked with water, agricultural & livestock system, marin & coastal ecosystems, and urban settlements)
- Management of disused and/or unused spaces (interlinked with water, biodiversity & ecosystems, urban settlements, marin & coastal ecosystems, and network & infrastructures)
- Cost-benefit monitoring (across all sectors)
- Green areas in general (across all sectors)
- Socioeconomic inequalities (across all sectors)
- Use of the “BES” questionnaire (Fair and Sustainable Welfare in Rome) (across all sectors)
- Involvement of associations in alert and monitoring systems (across all sectors)
- Strengthening the connection of existing networks of local associations (which are believed to be really able to reach where institutions may be lacking and provide support to those in need. This network undoubtedly represents a valuable resource that can be used and, indeed, enhanced to inform the population on adaptation issues and quickly understand the needs of communities that are often difficult to reach (across all sectors).

(*) Several of the elements included here could also be interlinked with elements of vulnerability. However, where highlighted by the groups, this has been written down. Therefore, the elements included here were explicitly decided upon among the group stakeholders.

Feedback from participants:

- Workshop organisation very much appreciated, although very challenging. General satisfaction for having had high-level discussions with truly active and relevant partners in the area.
- The interdisciplinary approach among groups has been appreciated, although some stakeholders (most of the time from the academy) took too much space in the discussion.
- Some participants expected a younger audience (between 20 and 40 years old).
- The division of colours for post-it was unclear for some tables.
- Some stakeholders in some groups pointed out that it would have been better to have facilitated the discussion more, instead of having the group act on its own decision.
- Many participants indicated their willingness to continue to be contacted in future workshops.
- We were asked to share the overall results, reports, as well as the next steps the city council will be undertaking based on the inception workshop.
- Most participants were eager to network with one another to create synergies with their organizations.

Conclusion and next steps

The results of the initial workshop will be used as a basis for further studies on vulnerability and adaptive capacity gaps/needs in the city of Rome. The next pilot phase is yet to be defined. Information from these activities will inform the work to be incorporated into Rome's Climate Change Adaptation Strategy (currently under development).

7.5 Annex 5 – Report Dresden Inception Workshop

Event title & rationale

AGORA - Inception Workshop in Dresden

The overarching goal of this workshop is to bring together a diverse group of stakeholders to discuss climate adaptation in Adaptation AGORA, laying the groundwork for future activities in the pilot region of Dresden and empowering the local community to collaborate effectively.

Specific Goal: To identify vulnerability and risk drivers and gaps in relation to local adaptive capacity through an assessment of local susceptibilities to the expected climate hazards, thereby aligning adaptation priorities and requirements with the needs of local communities (soft adaptation measure).

Date, Time and Location

16th of November 2023 13:45 – 19:00, citizens' lab of the city Dresden.

The citizens' lab (in German “Bürgerlabor”) became a reality as part of the “City of the Future” project in Dresden. Here, the city is testing how they can better engage citizens. This takes place through events, exhibitions and open consultation days in “pop-up style” where citizens, city

administration, politics and business are brought "to the table" to jointly advance innovative, citizen-oriented and digital developments in the city.

Holding the Adaptation AGORA inception workshop at the citizens' lab within the Dresden city hall showed the close partnership between the Adaptation AGORA team and the local government.

Agenda

13:45 Coffee & getting to know each other

14:00 Welcome and greeting

14:05 Introduction Adaptation AGORA project and the EU mission "Adaptation to Climate Change"

14:20 Icebreaker

14:40 Brainstorming session to co-explore context and priorities: Joint exploration of vulnerability factors and impacts of climate change on the different sectors based on a "problem tree analysis" (focus: heavy rain and heat waves)

15:40 Coffee break

16:00 Climate adaptation in Dresden: status, perspectives and common challenges

Representatives of the local government present the status of the climate adaptation strategy of the city of Dresden

Exchange and feedback from participants on their own measures and challenges in their sector with regard to climate adaptation

17:30 Conclusions, stakeholder expectations and next steps

18:00 Feedback and networking dinner

Number of participants, including from which Target Group

24 Participants

- [TG2] Academia: 5 participants
- [TG3] Governments and Decision-Makers / Authorities: 5 participants
- [TG4] Civil Society (which include TG1 - Local Communities): 10 participants
- [TG6] Investors / Private Sector: 4 participants

Other four participants were unable to attend last minute due to external reasons: two representing Governments and Decision-Makers/Authorities (Adaptation AGORA followers), one from the private sector, and one from the civil society in Dresden.

Executive summary

After a short presentation of Adaptation AGORA, the project and workshop's goals, people worked in groups to understand how Dresden is affected by climate change, especially with heatwaves and

heavy rainfall. More specifically, discussing and pointing out which sectors and population groups within these, were the most affected by these extreme events, as well as identifying the stakeholders and citizens adaptation gaps present in Dresden. This common understanding helped them look more closely at what the city is already doing to adapt to these challenges, which was presented by the environmental office of the City of Dresden. Participants then shared their experiences, talking about both their current and future activities and goals and the challenges they are facing in these efforts. Finally, the closure focused on the next steps and the stakeholders' wish of maintaining the adaptation network in the long term.

Key takeaways from each activity

The workshop participants identified several sectors and groups most affected by heat waves resulting from climate change. In terms of education, students are at higher risk to face disruptions in learning conditions, reduced opportunities on excessively hot days, and increased interest in climate change issues. The elderly population and infants/toddlers are particularly vulnerable to heat-related health issues, with potential impacts on cardiovascular health and social isolation. Socially vulnerable groups, such as low-income individuals and the homeless, lack access to resources (incl. access to air conditioning), while urban residents may experience the urban heat island effect. Public transportation users might face reliability challenges and heat shocks, and tourists may alter travel plans due to heatwaves. Outdoor workers, including construction and agricultural workers, are highly affected by being directly exposed to heat stress. Agricultural productivity may decline, affecting farmers and contributing to increased prices for low-income groups. Environmental factors such as noise, transportation issues, limited space, and overcrowding intensify the overall impact. The participants emphasized the importance of localized and accessible initiatives to address these diverse challenges.

Participants in the workshop pinpointed several sectors and groups heavily impacted by heavy rains and flooding. In terms of health, the elderly and children were identified as most susceptible to respiratory and musculoskeletal problems, with increased mental health concerns like fear, anxiety, isolation, and loneliness. Social vulnerability including shortages in emergency services, workplace disruptions, and financial losses for companies were described. For education, floods disrupt normal school operations, prompting students to miss classes for neighborhood support. Lack of knowledge on flood prevention measures and communication challenges during crises were highlighted. Housing, infrastructure, and urban planning emphasize the vulnerability of residents in low-lying areas, potential loss of housing, and challenges in historical preservation. Mobility and transportation face disruptions for commuters and travelers, impacting pedestrian and cycling traffic. Outdoor activities, including work for construction and agricultural workers, would face high risks. Agriculture sees crop failures affecting farmers, with financial challenges for low-income groups. Environmental factors include erosion, infrastructure destruction, and degraded water quality in rivers and lakes. The workshop underscored the need for resilience, structural precautions, and financial support mechanisms in the face of these diverse challenges.

In relation to adaptive capacity gaps in response to vulnerability risks from heavy rains and flooding due to climate change workshop participants highlighted the lack of awareness, particularly regarding heavy rainfall compared to flooding along the Elbe, was noted, urging increased focus on decision-makers and politicians for climate adaptation efforts. The importance of early warning systems, reactivity, and thoughtful deliberation in addressing climate risks were emphasized. Administrative challenges included the need to make climate adaptation mandatory in administration. Urban planning initiatives like the "Sponge City" project and decommissioning public spaces were underscored, addressing rainwater retention and transforming streets into tree-filled areas. Funding gaps for heavy rain damage were identified, proposing a public limited company, "Sponge City Dresden - AG Schwammstadt", for investment and expansion in infiltration and drainage areas. Homeowner engagement, particularly in decommissioning and green roofs, was advocated, emphasizing incentives for active participation. Lastly, community involvement and expertise were recognized as essential, urging the utilization of citizens' knowledge in climate adaptation initiatives.

Workshop participants identified key takeaways regarding adaptive capacity gaps in response to vulnerability risks from heat waves. Information and knowledge gaps encompassed the lack of awareness of individual action possibilities, absence of tailored information, limited access to technology, insufficient knowledge about materials for heat protection, and a lack of risk perception. Resource and infrastructure gaps included insufficient time and political recognition for volunteers, the need for connected green spaces, limited financial resources for educational programs, and challenges in making climate adaptation mandatory in administration.

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration gaps were highlighted describing the mismatch between the issue's importance and decision-makers' awareness, limited citizen engagement, and the need for trans sectoral partnerships. Preparedness and planning gaps featured the absence of a municipal heat action plan, the need for prioritizing heat-related considerations, and the importance of early warning systems. Empowerment and behavioural gaps were mentioned with a focus on calls for empowering individuals, addressing emotional responses, and simplifying complexity for concrete actions. Gaps in stakeholder roles and responsibilities were also identified, emphasizing the appointment of a Saxon Heat Coordinator and additional targeting of decision-makers and politicians.

State of the art on climate adaptation and finding common issues/challenges

This activity aimed to gather the adaptation measures implemented by the stakeholders in the workshop and identify common challenges. This should serve as a basis for potential future collaborations among stakeholders and for the Adaptation AGORA project to identify:

- What activities stakeholders are already carrying out or are willing to carry out, and
- What barriers they encounter and where the Adaptation AGORA project could support them.

The overall main issues identified will, therefore, serve as feedback and a basis for starting to implement future Adaptation AGORA's activities in Dresden (e.g., defining the content of the focus groups).

The activity began with a presentation by a member of the environmental office of the city of Dresden about the city's adaptation strategy, which is being finalized and is due for publication in 2024. The presentation began with a description of how the climate has changed in Dresden over the past decades and the resulting risks and impacts, both in terms of heatwaves and heavy rains/floods.

The presenter then described the city's adaptation strategy and its main action lines:

- Health - Heat stress
- Water - Risk of flooding due to river floods and heavy rainfall
- Urban greenery - Vitality of the vegetation

The presenter provided several examples of climate adaptation measures that the city has already implemented, along with opportunities for stakeholders (mostly property owners and constructors) and citizens to contribute or get informed. Some examples include the municipal policy "Dresden builds green" (in German, "Dresden baut grün"), tree plantings for regulating temperature and airflows in the city, climate-adapted schoolyard design, informational portals for climate-adapted buildings, and other possibilities for citizens such as watering street trees or engaging in community gardens.

The adaptation strategy of the city offered a framework for further explorations of other stakeholders' activities and challenges. Participants had the opportunity to present how they already engaged with climate adaptation and/or citizen engagement, what they would like to do more and what challenges they encounter in the process.

Participants, with support from the Adaptation AGORA team and the moderator, identified key challenges through an open discussion, categorizing them into financial and resource constraints, engagement and communication barriers, and technical and operational hurdles. Financial and resource constraints are marked by citizens and civic society organizations relying on volunteers and personal resources, leading to burnout and limited capacity, while project-based funding schemes hinder long-term planning. Engagement and communication barriers involve difficulty reaching marginalized groups, a lack of understanding and valuing citizen expertise, a rural-urban divide limiting educational opportunities, and challenges in translating academic knowledge for citizens. Technical and operational hurdles encompass excessive bureaucracy, slow digital infrastructure, competition for land, and an absence of binding regulations for buildings and construction, collectively highlighting the multifaceted challenges facing climate adaptation and citizen engagement initiatives.

Ongoing activities in the realm of climate change adaptation and engagement encompass a multifaceted approach. In the domain of engagement and communication, efforts are directed towards promoting a shared vision of climate change and adaptation with a focus on positive goals, utilizing community spaces like gardens, and developing informational portals such as the Smart City Model and climate-adapted building InkliBau. Hands-on laboratories and practical activities are organized to bridge the knowledge-action gap, employing tools like Bürgerlabor, initialization-room, and new participation formats for citizen engagement. Community management tools, the Cleema app, blogs, and social media are leveraged for outreach, while educational events at schools aim to motivate and inspire students. An online platform is under development to empower citizens and civil society in project development, and heat flyers are distributed for behavioral guidance during heat waves. Technical and operational activities include the establishment of the "sponge city" working group, urban greening initiatives like roof and wall greening, street trees, and river renaturation. Solar-green roofs, roof greening, external shadowing, rainwater cisterns, and a heat protection plan for health facilities are implemented as part of the ongoing efforts to address climate change challenges.

In aspiring towards effective climate adaptation solutions, key takeaways include the validation of new approaches through data-driven city planning and improved collaboration among municipal departments. Strengthening networking and collaboration involves fostering partnerships among various stakeholders and facilitating knowledge transfer from policymakers and academia to citizens. Communicating climate change positively is emphasized, with a focus on solutions and empowerment, requiring persuasion efforts to demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of green infrastructure. Designing funding programs for continuity and impact involves moving beyond project-based funding and ensuring ongoing support for implementation. To expand climate education, integrating it into school curricula is suggested, allowing more space for real-life education and flexibility. Partnering with marginalized groups is crucial for reaching a broader audience. Empowering young people is recognized as pivotal, urging recognition of youth as a core target group and sharing successful examples of youth engagement initiatives. Lastly, support from higher administration levels is deemed essential, encouraging collaboration and knowledge sharing between municipalities and regional authorities.

References and additional information

Problem tree analyses:

Heat waves

The participants in the workshop identified several sectors and groups of people most affected by heat waves, as a consequence of climate change. Here is a summary of the main takeaways:

Educational impact

students: heatwaves can disrupt normal school operations and impact students' learning conditions. Schools without adequate cooling systems may lead to discomfort and reduced concentration.

- reduced educational opportunities due to excessively hot days
- stressed learning environments
- increased interest in climate change issues
- decreased performance and productivity
- desire to implement local and easily accessible projects

Health impact

elderly population: older adults are particularly vulnerable to heatwaves, experiencing heat-related illnesses such as heatstroke and heat collapse. Existing health issues may worsen, and there is an increased risk of cardiovascular problems. Also avoiding public spaces due to heat, leading to isolation.

infants and toddlers: small children are also at risk due to potential difficulties regulating their body temperature. Infants and toddlers are more susceptible to dehydration and heat-related illnesses.

isolated or vulnerable individuals: prolonged heatwaves can promote social isolation and worsen mental health issues, especially in individuals already isolated or vulnerable.

- direct and indirect health effects of heat
- health implications, including slower wound healing and potential reduction in medication effectiveness
- general impact on concentration for all population groups, especially during tropical nights
- avoiding public spaces due to heat, (specially elderly population) leading to isolation

Social vulnerability

low-income and economically disadvantaged groups: individuals with limited financial resources may lack access to air conditioning, adequate housing, and healthcare, making them more vulnerable to the impacts of heat. High energy consumption for cooling during heatwaves can result in higher electricity bills, affecting low-income households.

homeless individuals: homeless individuals are exposed to extreme heat without protection and may face an increased risk of dehydration and heat-related illnesses.

Housing and urban planning

residents of urban areas: in the urban areas of dresden, the urban heat island effect can lead to significantly higher temperatures, especially in densely populated neighborhoods. Residents in these areas are at a greater risk of heat-related health problems.

- overheated buildings and apartments
- adverse effects on material properties under heat
- growing distrust in city planning and politics
- negative impact on city centers, affecting trade and alternative uses
- housing locations based on rent prices and financial resources
- vulnerability of (climate) refugees and migrants

Mobility and transportation

public transportation users: public transportation may be less reliable during extreme heat, causing inconvenience for those dependent on it.

- challenges for pedestrians and cyclists
- affects transport to city centers, affecting trade and alternative uses
- concerns about safety in transportation

Public spaces and events

tourists and recreational enthusiasts: heatwaves can influence travel plans and leisure activities, discouraging tourism and affecting local businesses.

elderly population avoiding public spaces due to heat.

- risks to outdoor activities and events in public spaces, parks, and city nature
- challenges and limitations on outdoor mobility (pedestrian and cyclist pathways)

Outdoor work

construction workers, agricultural workers, etc.: Outdoor workers, such as construction workers and farmers, are exposed to the direct effects of extreme heat, leading to heat stress, dehydration, and heat-related injuries.

Agriculture

farmers and agricultural workers: heatwaves can cause crop failures and reduce agricultural productivity, affecting farmers and agricultural workers.

low-income and economically disadvantaged groups: individuals with limited financial resources may be more affected by increasing prices of agricultural products due to crop failures and agricultural productivity reduction.

Environmental factors

Noise (open windows?/public transport?)

Transportation issues (higher towards places with high density such as city center and higher traffic areas)

Limited space and overcrowding (in city)

High temperatures + Intensification of outdoor heat by air conditioning systems

Heavy Rains and Floods

Participants in the workshop identified several sectors and groups most affected by heavy rains and flooding, consequences of climate change. The main takeaways from their discussions include:

Educational impact

students: floods can disrupt normal school operations. Students are also encouraged to miss classes to support their neighborhoods and city in case of large flooding events.

- Lack of knowledge on strategies: identified a lack of knowledge about flood prevention measures, emphasizing the need for regional concepts
- Communication challenges: lack of accessibility and communication during crises

Health impact

elderly population: older individuals are more susceptible to health issues due to dampness and cold. They may face an increased risk of respiratory and musculoskeletal problems.

children: children are sensitive to health risks associated with wet conditions and may be prone to colds and respiratory illnesses.

Mental health: increase in fear and anxiety

Mental health: isolation and loneliness, particularly in the face of floods at home, were highlighted

Social vulnerability

Shortages in emergency services: firefighters can face challenges due to insufficient personnel and resources.

Workplace disruptions: disruptions in daily work routines, also due to power outages.

Companies suffering financial losses: companies may suffer financial losses due to flooding and disruptions in business operations.

Housing, infrastructure and urban planning

residents in low-lying areas: people living near rivers or in low-lying areas are particularly vulnerable to flooding, facing significant property damage.

tenants and homeowners: heavy rains can lead to water infiltrations in homes, causing both financial and housing-related problems.

- Loss of housing: due to floods and damages to buildings.
- Preservation challenges: concerns about damages to buildings and infrastructure under historical preservation.

- Resilience to heavy rainfall: recognized the importance of building resilience to intense rainfall, and structural building precautions.
- Disruption of power and water supply: floods can disrupt power and water supply, leading to disruptions in daily life.

Mobility and transportation

commuters and travelers: intense rainfall can lead to traffic disruptions, affecting commuters and travelers. Road closures and delays in public transportation are possible.

Impact on pedestrian and cycling traffic: concerns for pedestrian and cycling traffic during heavy rains and floods.

Public spaces and events

Outdoor activities of civil society at risk: threats to outdoor activities due to heavy rains and floods.

Outdoor work

construction workers, agricultural workers, etc.: Outdoor workers, such as construction workers and farmers, affected by flood risk in specific locations: workplace disruptions due to floods.

Agriculture

farmers and agricultural workers: floods can cause crop failures and reduce agricultural productivity, affecting farmers and agricultural workers.

low-income and economically disadvantaged groups: individuals with limited financial resources may be more affected by increasing prices of agricultural products due to crop failures and agricultural productivity reduction.

High costs of recovery: substantial costs associated with post-crisis recovery.

Financial support: need for (low-threshold) financing and funding mechanisms.

Environmental factors

Erosion: identified as a significant concern.

Infrastructure Destruction: Concerns about the destruction of infrastructure and buildings.

Flood Risk in Specific Locations: Identified workplaces near rivers as prone to flooding.

Water Quality in Rivers and Lakes: Intense rainfall can degrade water quality in rivers and lakes, impacting the environment in nature reserves.

Heavy rains and flooding adaptive capacity gaps

Awareness and focus

Lack of awareness for heavy rain (elbe focus):

Participants noted a lack of awareness specifically regarding heavy rainfall, with more attention given to flooding along the elbe.

Additional target group - decision-makers/politicians:

The need for increased focus on decision-makers and politicians as an additional target group for climate adaptation efforts.

Early warning systems

Recognition of the importance of early warning systems for effective climate adaptation.

Reactivity and deliberation

Highlighted the importance of reactive measures and thoughtful deliberation in the face of climate risks.

Administrative challenges

Challenge in making climate adaptation mandatory in administration:

Participants highlighted that climate adaptation is not considered a mandatory task in administration, making a shift in focus challenging.

Urban planning and decommissioning

Rainwater retention management - "sponge city" project (schwammstadt)

Decommissioning of public spaces (streets to trees):

Emphasis on the decommissioning of public spaces, such as converting streets into areas with trees instead of parking spaces.

Funding and financial gaps

Lack of public funding for heavy rain damage:

Identified a gap in public funding for damages caused by heavy rainfall.

Public limited company (stock corporation) "sponge city" - ag schwammstadt:

To ensure investment and expansion of infiltration and drainage areas--> unsealing.

Homeowner engagement

Empowering homeowners - decommissioning and green roofs:

Advocacy for strengthening the engagement of homeowners in initiatives related to decommissioning and green roofs.

Incentives for homeowners' engagement:

Call for the creation of incentives to encourage homeowners to actively participate in decommissioning and the installation of green roofs.

Community involvement and expertise

Utilizing citizens' expertise:

Recognition of the need to tap into the expertise of the community, emphasizing the use of citizens' knowledge.

Heat waves adaptive capacity gaps

Information and knowledge gaps

- Lack of awareness of individual action possibilities.
- Absence of tailored and relevant information.
- Limited access to necessary technology.
- Insufficient knowledge about materials and constructions for heat protection.
- Lack of knowledge on the preferred and accepted measures by various actors.
- Limited knowledge on the effectiveness and feasibility of adaptation measures.
- Lack of risk perception.
- Limited knowledge on physical effects.

Resource and infrastructure gaps

- Insufficient time resources for volunteers.
- Lack of political recognition and potential compensation for volunteers.
- Lack of connected green spaces.
- Limited financial resources for implementing educational programs.
- Need for promotion of structural precautions.
- Insufficient resources in city administration.
- Lack of municipal heat action plan.
- Absence of regulations, guidelines, laws, etc.
- Challenges in making climate adaptation a mandatory task in administration.

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration gaps

- Mismatch between the importance of the issue and decision-makers' awareness and acceptance.
- Limited acceptance of the importance of the issue by decision-makers.
- Lack of citizen engagement due to feelings of being overwhelmed.
- Limited awareness of citizens' roles in addressing heat-related challenges.
- Need for trans sectoral partnerships.
- Focus on neighbourhood spaces and network building.

Preparedness and planning gaps

- Absence of an existing municipal heat action plan.
- Need for prioritization of heat-related considerations in planning.
- Emphasis on systemic thinking and understanding the interaction between climate protection and adaptation.
- Existing hitzwarnsystem without binding measures.
- The challenge in making climate adaptation a mandatory task in administration.
- Lack of preparedness through courses and training on the impacts of heat for various groups.
- Need for early warning systems.

- The importance of courses and training on the impacts of heat for different groups.

Empowerment and behavioural gaps

- Calls for empowering individuals with information on what they can do for their buildings and health.
- Emotional responses like fear, avoidance, and feelings of being overwhelmed.
- Advocacy for simplifying complexity for concrete action spaces within the everyday world.
- Lack of empowerment regarding individual contributions to addressing heat-related challenges.

Specific infrastructure measures

- Consideration of airflow and ventilation in urban design.
- Designing footpaths and bus stops to be heat-resilient.
- Strategies for heat storage for colder periods.
- Building insulation and energy retrofitting.

Stakeholder roles and responsibilities

- Appointment of a saxon heat Coordinator.
- Additional targeting of decision-makers and politicians as an audience.

Challenges & activities

Through an open discussion participants, supported by the Adaptation AGORA team and the moderator, clustered their challenges as follows.

Challenges

- Financial and resource constraints:
 - Citizens and civic society organizations often rely on volunteers and personal resources, leading to burnout and limited capacity; at the same time there are big expectations from civil society actors, leading to a lot of pressure (mostly on the younger people).
 - Project-based funding schemes hinder long-term planning and sustainability.
 - Limited financial and personal resources restrict time for climate adaptation and citizen engagement projects.
- Engagement and communication barriers:
 - Difficulty reaching marginalized groups, such as young people and vulnerable populations.
 - Lack of understanding and valuing citizen expertise and potential.
 - Rural-urban divide limits access to educational opportunities for rural communities.
 - Difficulty translating academic knowledge into accessible and actionable information for citizens.
- Technical and operational hurdles:

- Excessive bureaucracy impedes project development and implementation.
- Slow and inadequate digital infrastructure.
- Competition for land for technical projects and community spaces.
- Absence of binding regulations for buildings and construction.

Ongoing activities

- Engagement and communication
 - Promoting a shared vision of climate change and adaptation, emphasizing positive goals and encouraging patience.
 - Exploring the potential of community spaces, such as gardens, to reach a diverse audience.
 - Developing informational portals, such as Smart City Model and climate-adapted building InkliBau.
 - Organizing hands-on laboratories and practical activities to bridge the gap between knowledge and action.
 - Utilizing Bürgerlabor, initialization-room, and new participation formats to engage citizens from the center to the neighborhoods.
 - Leveraging community management tools, the Cleema app, blogs, and social media for outreach.
 - Hosting educational events at schools to motivate and inspire students.
 - Developing an online platform to empower citizens and civil society to participate in project development and implementation.
 - Distributing heat flyers to provide guidelines for behavior during heat waves and inform about health impacts.
 - Developing climate adaptation strategies, e.g. in health facilities and educating employers about the risks of heat and how to react
- Technical and operational activities
 - Working group "sponge city".
 - Implementing urban greening initiatives, such as roof and wall greening, street trees, and river renaturation.
 - Installing solar-green roofs.
 - Implementing roof greening, external shadowing, and rainwater cisterns.
 - Developing a heat protection plan for health facilities to cool down patient rooms.

Aspirations and potential solutions

- Validate new approaches and solutions:
 - Develop data-driven city planning strategies.
 - Enhance collaboration and feedback integration among municipal departments.
- Strengthen networking and collaboration:

- Foster partnerships among various stakeholders.
- Facilitate knowledge transfer from policymakers and academia to citizens.
- Communicate climate change positively:
 - Emphasize solutions and empowerment.
 - Need to do a lot of persuasion work to show that green infrastructure is not only worth it, but also not as much effort or damage as many people think.
- Design funding programs for continuity and impact:
 - Move beyond project-based funding.
 - Ensure funding for implementation and real-world impact.
- Expand climate education:
 - Integrate climate education into school curricula: leave more space for real-life education and more flexibility in the planning of the educational activities, leaving also space for engagement (e.g. free days from school).
 - Partner with marginalized groups to reach a broader audience.
- Empower young people:
 - Recognize young people as a core target group, not just an afterthought.
 - Share successful examples of youth engagement initiatives.
- Provide support from higher administration levels:
 - Encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing between municipalities and regional authorities.

